

D4.5

Updated policy landscape in ENVRI domain

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Deliverable abstract

This document provides an assessment of the progress from 2020-2023 in developing FAIR data policies within ENVRI-FAIR environmental research infrastructures. In particular, it a comparison with D4.2 which provided the initial landscape survey is given. The text describes the progress made in advancing ENVRI research infrastructures towards FAIRness, and the diagrams provide ‘heat maps’ where the colour indicates the state. The conclusion is that much progress has been achieved, but – as always – there is more that could be done, with varying amounts to be done in the different RIs. It is of particular importance that progress on the ‘legal policies’ has been rapid and is almost completed for the RIs of ENVRI.

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	Name	Partner Organisation	Date
Main Author	Mairi Best	FZJ	27 June 2023
Contributing Authors	Helen Glaves Ari Asmi	UKRI BGS UHEL / RDA Europe	28 June 2023 01 July 2020
Reviewer(s)	Keith Jeffery	UKRI BGS	10 July 2023
Approver	Andreas Petzold	FZJ	13 July 2023

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions, and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D4.5 - Updated policy landscape in ENVRI domain

1 Introduction and Purpose*

Wider adoption and implementation of the FAIR principles¹ has been instrumental in cementing open science practices throughout the community of research infrastructures of the environmental science cluster (ENVRI community) and beyond. However, these principles are extremely general by design and, despite the commentaries provided by the FORCE11 group² and other associated initiatives (e.g., GO-FAIR³), much of the detail and definitions are left open to interpretation as part of the implementation layer. This makes alignment with these principles relatively straightforward, but creation of an integrated data system more difficult in practice. However, due to the usefulness of the FAIR principles, they have been widely adopted. For the purposes of this deliverable, the most important application of FAIR is integration of the participating RIs with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), which has determined these principles as some of the most important requirements for being part of the EOSC (data) services.

The requirements of the FAIR principles can be approached from a technical perspective through identification of the solutions required for their implementation. In the context of ENVRI-FAIR, this analysis has been undertaken by WP5 and documented in the recently published deliverable D5.1 on Requirement Analysis, Technology Review and Gap Analysis of Environmental RIs⁴. However, this technical perspective can sometimes be incomplete because the changes in organisational structures, stakeholder requirements, technical management and (perhaps most importantly in this context) external technical developments can lead to any such landscape analysis being incomplete in terms of the overall goals and objectives of the individual research infrastructures (RIs). A comprehensive understanding of existing relevant policies, rules, and strategies is key, and in many cases the existing practices might not have been properly considered from the perspective of the organisational goals and needs. That is to say that practices might have been organically created at some level of the organisation that, while fitting a specific need, might not map well on to the long-term objectives of the RI as a whole.

Another aspect of this deliverable is the concept of *organisational debt*⁵ in the current environmental ESFRI RIs with regards to FAIR data services. This term means that some aspects of an RI's operations have not been completely decided or clearly defined during the RI development phase. Sometimes these kinds of organisational debts are a direct result of the non-alignment of organisational development, due to outside influences, or a lack of decision-making bodies. As with any form of debt, the longer key aspects remain undecided, the “interest” – in this case the effort to actually codify already existing possibly divergent practices – increases and ultimately requires more work. Absorbing this type of debt is a natural result of any rapid organisational development, but it also needs to be understood and mapped, and the associated risks should be readily known in the RI management. ESFRI RIs in the environmental sciences are highly heterogeneous, and have a wide range of organisational, technical, and operational readiness levels, which is often evident from the existing policies that have been put in place.

This kind of analysis is commonly called a *landscape analysis* and it is the subject of this deliverable. However, for the landscape analysis to be useful⁶, it must be well targeted (which kinds of organisations are involved), well scoped (what kind of information is collected), and feasible (how much information is collected). All these aspects are considered in the next section.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² <https://www.force11.org/fairprinciples>

³ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/3884998>

⁵ This term is analogous to “documentation debt” or “programming debt” used in software development, where suboptimal or poorly commented code is allowed to be a part of the production software due to time or resource constraints. Usually, such practice will lead to increased overall costs (i.e., “interest”), but can be useful or even critical for success.

*Significant text repeated here is derived from *D4.2 Policy Landscape in ENVRI Domain*, to maintain parallel structure with the earlier analysis and reiterate the rationale behind the questionnaire design.

⁶ This section is based on the experiences from H2020 RISCAPe project, which analyzed the landscape of the international (i.e., non-EU) research infrastructures globally (manuscript in preparation, but some aspects available in the final report: <https://zenodo.org/record/3539254>)

2 Methods*

Details of the initial approach to designing the policy survey questionnaire are provided in D4.2 “Policy landscape in the ENVRI domain”. In addition, narrowing of the scope of policies was done through a series of four policy workshops run throughout the ENVRI-FAIR project. Information in this section is repeated and updated from D4.2 to provide basic context for the following sections.

2.1 Definitions and targets

As mentioned in the introduction, a landscape analysis first needs to clearly define the goal of the analysis, the kinds of information collected, identify the target organisations, and based on these, select the methodology and analysis methods.

2.1.1 Analysis Framework:

- 1) The goal is to understand the minimal set of key policies (see section 2.3) needed for FAIR data services in the context of ENVRI-FAIR, and to support RI interoperability with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). These policies need to be either harmonised, or at least documented in a harmonised way, as part of a common policy framework. To achieve this objective, WP4 conducted a landscape analysis across the participating RIs to determine the current status and immediate plans for adopting and/or implementing the identified key policies in a comparable and useful format.
- 2) The information collected needed to be relevant for creating common policies across the ENVRI-FAIR RIs for delivery of interoperable FAIR data services to the EOSC.
- 3) Target organisations are the ENVRI-FAIR RIs or the representing partners where there is currently no single legal entity.
- 4) The chosen methodology was based on conducting virtual interviews and online questionnaires using a series of predefined questions that were supplied to the interviewee before the meeting (section 5.1 below).

2.1.2 Overall Interview Process:

- a. The interviewees were contacted by email to explain the overall purpose of the interview, and to share the information package (section 5.1 below).
- b. Follow-up emails or virtual meetings were used to clarify any questions, and to improve the response rate.
- c. Within the questionnaire, the RI personnel were first informed about the purpose of the interview and the process involved. Their consent was then confirmed.
- d. The questionnaire was in the form of a spreadsheet in Google Drive which contained the questions and answers previously collected from that specific RI during the previous survey in 2020. Only the interviewees of a particular RI have access to that RIs spreadsheet.
- e. After the interviewees had filled in the responses to the same questions as part of the current survey, the answers were compiled into a master spreadsheet for analysis.

2.1.3 What is a policy?

*1b) a **definite** course or method of action selected from among alternatives and in light of given conditions to **guide and determine present and future decisions***

Merriam Webster Dictionary

The term is used in many different ways, varying from institution to institution, organisation to organisation and sometimes within institutions and organisations as well. It can be hard to pin down, but there are some central features common to all good policy:

- *it states **matters of principle***
- *it is focused on **action**, stating what **is to be done and by whom***
- *it is an **authoritative statement**, made by a person or body with power to do so.*

Above all, good policy is a tool which makes administration easier, and allows people to get on with the organisation's core business more efficiently and effectively.

Australian policy handbook

*A policy is a deliberate **system of principles** to **guide decisions** and achieve rational outcomes. A policy is a **statement of intent**, and is **implemented as a procedure or protocol**. Policies are generally adopted by a governance body within an organization. Policies can assist in both subjective and objective decision making. Policies to assist in subjective decision making usually assist senior management with decisions that must be based on the relative merits of a number of factors, and as a result are often hard to test objectively. In contrast policies to assist in objective decision making are usually operational in nature and can be objectively tested, e.g. password policy*

Wikipedia on "Policy", retrieved 10.7.2019

We consider organisational rules, best practices, and operating methods of the research infrastructure to be *policies* in this document. They are formal rules of operation, and typically are not explicitly technology dependent, but are instead meant for the staff and contributors (humans) to implement inside their organisation (RI in this case). They are the local standards for people working within the organisation. However, it is important to note that the interaction between technical standards and policies is complex, and in many cases they do not intersect in a way that leads to specific technical requirements, or the existing technological limitations directly influence policies.

Policies can exist in a written policy document, but sometimes they are only unwritten practices or de-facto operational procedures within an organisation. However, some policies may be completely lacking, or there can be many conflicting versions of existing practices, and even different interpretations of written policies.

For further discussion see "General expected aspects of ENVRI RI policies" in D4.2.

2.1.4 Interoperability goals

As ENVRI-FAIR is aiming towards interoperable ENVRI services, there is a need to define what interoperability means in this context. There are many types and levels of service interoperability, which can be defined from very general to extremely detailed technical levels. In the loosest sense, interoperability does already exist in practically all available research services as, with enough (manual) work, reading of manuals and communication with authors, one can (in theory) join almost any service with another. However, this is not usually considered to be interoperability in the context of ENVRI-FAIR.

In the strictest sense, interoperability would mean that every service provided by the RIs (data, visualisations, metadata, analysis tools) would be completely interchangeable, using the same formats, metadata, vocabularies, terminologies, interfaces, access methods and terms, licences etc. This would

mean that all of their services could be “dropped-in” to compatible virtual research environments (VREs) or similar platforms. This level of interoperability can currently only be achieved in a single RI product catalogue or, in some rare cases, over a smaller subset of the ENVRI services, e.g., within a single sub-domain. Due to practical considerations, the full interoperability described above is unlikely to be feasible for the ENVRI community. WP4 in ENVRI-FAIR worked towards determining the realistic level of interoperability achievable and adjusted the target level of the work accordingly.

From the perspective of user communities, the ENVRI-FAIR mission can be considered to be creating an environmental research catalogue of services, which are usable with each other with *minimal additional effort* from the user communities.

This means that we do not directly aim for full interoperability of all services, with complete canonical integration. Instead, we aim towards *well documented service (and policy) interfaces, with (minimal set of) common elements needed for service integration*. From the policy point of view, it suggests that each individual policy does not need to be identical. They only have to be identical from the service interaction interface perspective, i.e., where they are critical to the interaction between individual services.

2.2 From requirements to the interview questions

Analysis of the FAIR principles and the associated descriptions were used to derive an initial list of policy requirements for FAIR service provision. This list was then analysed to produce a reduced list of questions (see section 5.1), which is based on the identified potential policies, and the information that can be realistically collected.

It was recognised that to maximise the potential benefit of this landscape analysis, rather than capturing a single ‘snapshot’ of the current status of policy adoption and implementation within the participating RIs, information should be captured more than once during the ENVRI-FAIR project. This then helps to understand how the adoption of these policies with the ENVRI community has evolved during the lifetime of the project. Due to impacts of the COVID-19 crisis and then a change in personnel in WP4, both the 2020 and 2023 interviews were severely delayed. This version of the landscape analysis (and deliverable 4.5) presents the current situation as of June 2023, and includes all the participating RIs.

A suite of policy categories was refined through a series of four policy workshops throughout the ENVRI-FAIR project.

(<https://training.envri.eu/course/search.php?search=policy>). As a result, it was identified that both policies for legality and for interoperability were needed. Those for legal protection are dealt with in D4.3 “Report on legal and IPR aspects of service policies in the ENVRI domain”. The state at the time of this second landscape survey is recorded in (Figure 1). Policy categories identified for interoperability are:

- Licensing
- Authorisation/Authentication
- Metadata (FAIR)
- Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement
- Curation

These categories were used to group the questions developed in the first policy questionnaire (see D4.2 and section 5.1).

This version of the landscape analysis (D4.5) presents the current situation as of May/June 2023 and includes all of the RIs participating in ENVRI-FAIR. (Note: EMSO and EPOS did not participate in the 2020 iteration of the analysis). The next section documents the interview questions and answers, results from both 2020 and 2023, together with a discussion of progress and final results for each question.

3 Results

Questions used in the preliminary policy landscape analysis (D4.2) have been rearranged by policy category, namely: Licensing, Authorisation/Authentication, Metadata (FAIR), Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement and Curation (see discussion above). Note: number in brackets at the end of each question in this section refers to its original number in the 2020 survey (see Appendix 5.1 and D4.2). In the following, the “Background and Purpose sections have been reproduced from D4.2 for consistency with the original rationale of the questionnaire.

In general, RIs that are operational have already implemented the various policies, and those that are currently forming are in the process of implementation. That said, though some RIs are not operational as a pan-European entity, their community cooperation and practice sometimes put them ahead of more mature EU RIs in some elements of policy.

When the policy item exists as a practice rather than a policy, this is noted.

3.1 Licencing

3.1.1 Do you have chosen a licence for your data? If so, which one? Are multiple licences applied? (1)

3.1.1.1 Background and Purpose

Licences are a crucial part of the data provision, as they describe to the user communities what they are able to do with the (meta)data provided. Licences are important from the ENVRI-FAIR perspective because this information is needed to create an interoperability layer for combining the services. The requirement is driven mostly from the definition of “Accessible” in FAIR but is crucial for “Interoperable” (especially for machine-readable form). A notable additional point is that all of the interviews specifically concentrated on the “core data” (if defined) for the RI, and not so much on additional data stored in the RI systems, which can be either legacy datasets, campaign-type data repositories, or other ancillary data.

3.1.1.2 Progress and Final Results

All RIs have chosen a licence or licences that specify the purposes that an individual can make of the data based on their status (researcher, commercial company etc.). Most use creative commons licences CC-BY 4.0, CC-BY-NC; an exception is EISCAT’s internal licence. Some have multiple licences while trying to harmonise across pre-existing national/data provider licences (e.g., AnaEE).

As stated in D4.2, the existence of national and local licences (sometimes for tighter use constraints) was again raised, particularly for those RIs dependent on the data collection from their national institutions. In some cases, use of such licences was required by national laws or regulations, making harmonisation even more challenging. Heterogeneity of licences seem to be higher for RIs with less centralised data collection procedures, some are working on an analysis of legal interoperability of the partner RIs. In some cases, the licence is completely defined by the contributing RIs, but (e.g., AnaEE) multiple licencing for CC is being considered.

A limited suite of licences has been encouraged through ENVRI-Hub. The potential for double licencing is still necessary for the RIs not able to consolidate to one licence.

3.1.2 Is the license also applicable for your metadata? If not, what license is used for your metadata? (1.2)

3.1.2.1 *Background and Purpose*

Metadata do not always have the same attention to licences and explicit policies as data. If mentioned at all, it is often considered to be an integral part of the data, and therefore has the same licence. However, in practice, the metadata licence can differ from that of the data where their origins are not the same. For example, within distributed infrastructures the majority of the data comes from distributed nodes, but the metadata is at least partly completed by the RI itself. Furthermore, because the metadata and data can be used separately an explicit policy (and communication) for the metadata licence can be useful.

3.1.2.2 *Progress and Final Results*

In many cases, the same licence is applicable to the metadata. If not, generally it is because metadata are even more open (e.g., CC0). In practice, metadata is considered to be open (even if not explicitly licenced). Exceptions are usually due to security considerations (e.g., protected or endangered species).

3.1.3 Is the licence machine-readable? (1.1)

3.1.3.1 *Background and Purpose*

Machine readability is a crucial part of the interoperability and findability criteria for data. Determination of the applicable licence for each dataset is therefore a key criterion for identifying those datasets which are interoperable and compatible. The technical solution for implementing machine-readable licenses vary, but the main aspect in this question (as with others) is to map the potential for such policies. Inclusion of already existing systems is important if we consider machine-readable licenses to become a more common policy.

3.1.3.2 *Progress and Final Results*

Most RIs have a machine-readable licence policy, but in many cases this is within the metadata, and the format is not necessarily standardised across harvested data.

3.1.4 Do you have agreement with your data providers (if relevant) on the ownership and licencing of data? (7)

3.1.4.1 *Background and Purpose*

Sharing data and metadata via the RI platform requires the necessary permissions. In many cases this is via implicit agreements, which carries inherent risks such as questions on what can be done with the (meta)data in the future, or withdrawal of some of the data assets. Clear agreements with the data providers should be the norm unless the data provision is completely covered by the internal processes of the RIs.

3.1.4.2 *Progress and Final Results*

All RIs have a policy and agreements with data providers on data ownership and licensing where relevant. In some cases (eLTER, LifeWatch, DiSSCo, DANUBIUS), this aspect is in progress as the RI itself is under development and/or becoming an ERIC.

3.2 Authorisation and Authentication

3.2.1 Do you have an access policy for the data? (6)

3.2.1.1 Background and Purpose

Access services is a core RI function. A clear, available, transparent, and documented access policy is essential for “Accessibility” in the context of FAIR data, as well as for any operational system contributing to the EOSC.

3.2.1.2 Progress and Final Results

Most RIs are open access. Registration can be optional or required. Some are still sorting out access for data products and raw data from national sites/data providers.

3.2.2 What are the access formalities for data (or different kinds of data)? (6.1)

3.2.2.1 Background and Purpose

If the data is not available anonymously, the access protocols (even light ones) should follow a clear and transparent process, preferably documented in a policy.

3.2.2.2 Progress and Final Results

In many cases there are no access formalities, and registration is not required. Exceptions include access to raw data, data under revision, APIs, large data volumes, and services.

3.2.3 Is there a formal process for accessing restricted data (if relevant)? (6.2)

3.2.3.1 Background and Purpose

In the case of restricted data, having a clear access policy with a transparent review process, appropriate ethical guidelines, and the potential for corrective actions is clearly good practice. This question was mostly aimed at collecting relevant information on potential solutions from existing RIs.

3.2.3.2 Progress and Final Results

In most cases this is not applicable because there is no restricted data. Where data is restricted because of security concerns, embargoes, national licences (based on the affiliation country of the user and experimenter), information related to endangered species, etc. there are usually procedures in place.

3.2.4 Do you allow external authorisation (i.e., registration via another trusted source)? (6.3)

3.2.4.1 Background and Purpose

The capability to use results across different RIs would benefit from only needing a limited set of authorisations. A single-sign-on is not always possible, but there are clear advantages to sharing the authorisation or identification information between the RIs.

3.2.4.2 Progress and Final Results

With the exception of eLTER and EUROARGO, all RIs allow external authorisation or are in the process (ACTRIS) of implementing this functionality. For EUROARGO, this is simply not applicable because there is no registration/authorisation required.

3.2.5 Is the access policy available in machine-readable form? (6.5)

3.2.5.1 Background and Purpose

Unless the access policy is available in a machine-readable form, the access procedures (even if automated), typically require some form of human interaction.

3.2.5.2 Progress and Final Results

The access policies of ICOS, AnaEE, EUROARGO, EPOS are machine-readable, LifeWatch, DiSSCo and ACTRIS are in the process of implementing this option. The remaining RI access policies are not machine-readable.

3.3 Metadata (FAIR)

3.3.1 Does your data have included metadata? (4)

3.3.1.1 Background and Purpose

Metadata is central to the FAIR principles, and to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Without a clear policy to include metadata, and other associated policies, the FAIRness of the services is hard to evaluate, and interoperability is more difficult to achieve.

3.3.1.2 Progress and Final Results

All RIs have included metadata, though some (e.g., SIOS) are updating their historical data sets.

3.3.2 Does your RI's metadata follow some standard(s)? (4.1)

3.3.2.1 Background and Purpose

Metadata standards are vital for the findability and reusability of RI data. However, many of the applicable standards are quite general, but there are more detailed (i.e., use and interoperability) related metadata elements that are highly domain specific. To achieve some form of high-level interoperability between the RI data products requires the collecting and (if possible) harmonising or translating of these standards.

3.3.2.2 Progress and Final Results

All follow some standards, such as INSPIRE, Darwin Core, ISO..., and in some cases internal standards. Most have their own metadata model built on these standards, which is expanded according to subdomain-specific requirements.

3.3.3 Does your RI use-controlled vocabularies for metadata? (4.2)

3.3.3.1 *Background and Purpose*

Connected to the previous question, a policy to use-controlled vocabularies is a crucial part of a successful and interoperable metadata system. A related issue is the selection of these vocabularies, including how they are governed.

3.3.3.2 *Progress and Final Results*

All RIs use-controlled vocabularies for metadata, including CF, GCMD, GBIF, INSPIRE, OSGeo, EnvThes, and some internal vocabularies (e.g., ACTRIS, AnaEE, ARGO, ICOS).

3.3.4 Are these vocabularies controlled by your RI? (4.2.1)

3.3.4.1 *Background and Purpose*

If the vocabularies are controlled by the RI, they are generally more flexible and easier to update. However, such internal vocabularies also require maintenance and have long-term sustainability, and they can be harder to integrate into other systems. Common external vocabularies might be more challenging to implement and are outside the governance of the RI.

3.3.4.2 *Progress and Final Results*

Most RIs do not control the metadata vocabularies they use, an exception is for internal vocabularies (ACTRIS, AnaEE, ARGO, ICOS). Continued coordination on adjusting common external vocabularies would be a useful legacy of ENVRI-FAIR.

3.3.5 Does your RI have a policy/practice for quality control of metadata? (4.3)

3.3.5.1 *Background and Purpose*

Metadata quality is crucial, and QC/QA processes are part of most analyses of the FAIR principles. RIs should be well prepared to produce quality-controlled metadata (and data), and any associated policies are crucial.

3.3.5.2 *Progress and Final Results*

Most RIs practice quality control of metadata, or are implementing the same, with the exceptions of IAGOS and EISCAT. In some cases, QC is the responsibility of the original data provider. Quality information should be made available to the users.

3.3.6 Do you share your metadata? (4.4)

3.3.6.1 *Background and Purpose*

The FAIR principles, particularly the Findability criteria strongly suggest that metadata catalogues are openly available for external searches.

3.3.6.2 *Progress and Final Results*

All RIs share or are in the process of sharing their metadata. Good progress has been made over the duration of the project. Caveats include security considerations (e.g., protected or endangered species).

3.4 Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement

3.4.1 Do you have a definition of what is a dataset in your RI? (2)

This question refers to both scientific (i.e., variables involved) and practical (temporal, experiment, etc.) separation of each dataset (data granularity).

3.4.1.1 *Background and Purpose*

The FAIR principles include several mentions of the concept of data and dataset. However, the definition of these terms is not always clear. This creates a problem because a clear definition of a (domain dependent) dataset is required in order to assign persistent identifiers (PIDs), which provide usage information and track use of individual datasets. This is key for the Findability element of the FAIR principles and a pre-requisite for many other aspects of interoperability.

3.4.1.2 *Progress and Final Results*

All have some working definition of a dataset, which is a major advance during ENVRI-FAIR, but whether or not this has been formalised or harmonised varies. For some RIs, the selection criteria are geographic and/or time based, while for others it is a single experiment, or a specific species, etc.

3.4.2 Do you define a data version? What are the policies/practices (if any) regarding versioning? (2.1)

3.4.2.1 *Background and Purpose*

Scientific outputs often require correction, re-calibration, and refinement as the methods for analysis improve. However, clear policies on what is defined as a “new” version vary, and methods and strategies to communicate changes in the data are not currently very common despite this being critical for reuse. Ideally, the RI data systems should manage the versioning of datasets, including directing users of earlier versions to the new ones (via the metadata or otherwise), and provide clear provenance information for all changes to the (meta) data.

3.4.2.2 *Progress and Final Results*

Versioning is widely considered by participating RIs. Some keep same PID, while others change with each version. How this is implemented also varies between continuous and discrete datasets. A common policy should more fully map these versioning strategies and define a standardised approach to describing them in the metadata available to users.

3.4.3 Do you have a policy on authorship of the data? (4.5)

3.4.3.1 *Background and Purpose*

Data authorship (usually described in the metadata) is a crucial element for following the data usage, and also offers an incentive for the national data producers to share their data. However, policies on who is actually identified in the metadata vary and are sometimes inconsistent even within a single RI. Additionally, the metadata can also include references to the RI data curation work.

3.4.3.2 *Progress and Final Results*

All RIs have or are implementing policies on authorship. Some have had these policies from the start, while others, such as eLTER and DANUBIUS, have made significant progress. For LifeWatch and EMSO, authorship currently depends on the source of the data. There remains significant variability in practice and policy between RIs with respect to data authorship and who is identified in the metadata.

3.4.4 Do you require users to cite or reference your data if used? If so, do you provide a clear definition of how this should be done? (6.4)

3.4.4.1 Background and Purpose

Most of the Participating RIs have reporting requirements for usage of their services. Distributed RIs are also dependent on the provision of their national nodes, which have their own challenges for demonstrating their impact. Having a clear policy on how to attribute the RI and the data producers is beneficial for measuring impact of the RI. A more consistent approach to citation/referencing would make use of results across RIs easier.

3.4.4.2 Progress and Final Results

Data citation/acknowledgement is recommended or required by all RIs, although it is still being implemented in some cases (EMSO, EPOS, DANUBIUS, DiSSCo). A number mention the challenge of enforcing this requirement/recommendation.

3.4.5 Do your datasets have a PID? Are there exceptions? (3)

3.4.5.1 Background and Purpose

Many of the FAIR principle definitions include the need for each dataset (see section 3.2) to have a (unique) persistent identifier. However, RI policies on this requirement are often non-existent or unclear. Having a clear PID policy is advantageous for RIs, especially if it is also clearly documented for users.

3.4.5.2 Progress and Final Results

All RIs have or are implementing PIDs for their datasets. Significant progress on the adoption of persistent identifiers has been made by the RIs since 2020 and the concerted efforts made in this area during ENVRI-FAIR have yielded positive results.

3.4.6 Which PID(s) do you use? Are they internal or external? (3.1)

3.4.6.1 Background and Purpose

Having a single policy defining the types of PIDs being used is important for users and the internal consistency of the RI. This will also avoid having multiple different ways to point to the same dataset. Internal PIDs have more flexibility, but external (especially widely used DOIs) have a much broader application area.

3.4.6.2 Progress and Final Results

While all RIs have (planned) PIDs, not all are DOIs and some are internal.

3.5 Curation

3.5.1 Does your data service have a service level agreement (or other way to define uptime goals, etc.)? (8)

3.5.1.1 Background and Purpose

Service level agreements are critical for several aspects of potential data use. The FAIR principles require that at least the metadata is available (see question 3.8.2), but more importantly from the EOSC point of

view is that new services can be built on those that already exist. In this respect, having a clear (and documented) policy on expected level of service is crucial for downstream users.

3.5.1.2 Progress and Final Results

ICOS, SIOS, AnaEE, EPOS, and EUROARGO have SLAs or an equivalent practice for data service monitoring. Those that monitor report >99% uptime. IAGOS, LifeWatch, DiSSCo, DANUBIUS, and EMSO are working on this aspect of their services.

3.5.2 Is there a policy for keeping data and metadata constantly available? (9)

3.5.2.1 Background and Purpose

This question is connected to an earlier section (3.8.1), but is more directly focused on the FAIR principles, where many of the interpretations specifically require that, as a minimum, the metadata is constantly available for users. As many services depend on federated metadata searches, such a requirement is understandable.

3.5.2.2 Progress and Final Results

There is in practice, however this rarely a formal policy. IAGOS, DiSSCo, and EMSO are currently developing such policies.

3.5.3 Do you have a policy for retention of data and metadata? (5)

3.5.3.1 Background and Purpose

Data and metadata retention are key features of data repositories, and having related plans and policies are critical for provenance, sustainability, usefulness, and trustworthiness of data.

3.5.3.2 Progress and Final Results

Few RIs currently have official retention policies, many have made progress throughout the project and are now implementing them. Almost all participating RIs have a policy of retaining all data (exception: EISCAT).

3.5.4 Do you have a described data deletion / reduction process? (5.1)

3.5.4.1 Background and Purpose

In some cases, there is a need for reducing and or deleting data. The original basis of this question was more focused on managing resource limitations (i.e., limited storage space), but other reasons for data deletion (e.g., geoinformation for species collection, GDPR compliance) could be also important for RI policies.

3.5.4.2 Progress and Final Results

Generally, RIs don't have a described data deletion/reduction process as few have formal data retention policies (see question 5, 3.5.3). Some exceptions are identified for reasons associated with the size of the datasets (EISCAT), security and ethics (DiSSCo), or legislation e.g., GDPR.

3.5.5 Do you have a policy/plan for data/metadata availability in the long-term (e.g., closure of the RI)? (5.2)

3.5.5.1 *Background and Purpose*

Metadata availability in the event of a data system closing down due to financial or other reasons is a minimal requirement for FAIR data. Also having a long-term preservation policy for the data itself would be preferable, especially in the environmental sciences where most observations are not repeatable. A clearly stated policy on this issue would also be desirable for the user communities.

3.5.5.2 *Progress and Final Results*

All RIs except ACTRIS have a long-term plan for data/metadata availability, although DiSSCo and EMSO are currently working on it.

3.6 Policy availability

3.6.1 Generally, do you have the RI policies/practices published in a findable and accessible way? Do they have PIDs?

3.6.1.1 *Background and Purpose*

A key aspect of policies is that they are available. However, not all of them can necessarily be included in the metadata for the services or data, but they should be FAIR. Having relevant policies as a pointer to the implemented policy document makes human interface possible.

3.6.1.2 *Progress and Final Results*

All RIs have some form of data policy: some are easier to find than others, some are in the process of being approved or implemented (see data policy URLs in Section 5.2, Table 28). Not all RIs have PIDs. The EUROARGO approach of publishing their policies in a best-practices journal is an interesting approach that might be replicated by other RIs.

4 Summary of Policy Progress and Status

The RI responses received show some common trends:

- There continues to be a need for policy development and harmonisation, particularly between RIs and their data providers.
- Many individual solutions should continue to be shared at the overall decision-making level, especially between the ENVRI subdomains.
- There is a clear understanding of the need for relatively formal policies, particularly in service definition and access, but continued work is needed to increase compatibility and avoid the need for human interpretation.

Much progress has been made on the policies for interoperability described in some detail above and represented as a ‘heat map’ in Figure 1. In addition, the essential associated ‘legal’ policies are described in *D4.3 Report on legal and IPR aspects of service policies in ENVRI domain* and represented as a ‘heat map’ in Figure 2.

This work will continue in the implementation of ENVRI-Hub and in association with ongoing policy development work in other EU-funded projects, e.g., FAIRsFAIR.

4.1 Policies for Interoperability

4.1.1 Policy Categories for Interoperability

The initial response (2020) and current (2023) RI status of the required policies for interoperability are shown in Figure 1. Questions used in the preliminary policy landscape analysis (D4.2) were rearranged by policy category: Licensing, Authorisation/Authentication, Metadata (FAIR), Provenance / Citation/ Acknowledgement and Curation (see discussion above). This figure is designed to be viewed as a heatmap, with a focus on the colour shading of the cells indicating the evolution of responses to the questions: green=yes, yellow=in progress/partial, red=no.

Figure 1 demonstrates that, while many RIs were well advanced in a number of areas at the beginning of the project (predominance of yellow and green), significant progress has been made during the project (shift from yellow to green for a number of RIs). Note, “no” (red) is not necessarily a lack of the policy, but sometimes a different decision by the RI in the context of the question; “in progress/partial” (yellow) is usually a function of the state of development of the RI overall. It should be noted that while most RI’s have reached a relatively mature stage of policy development, not all policies are necessarily aligned with each other or with the ENVRI-Hub. This is being addressed across ENVRI by multiple licences, harmonisation within a given RI (which often in turn represents a consortium of data providers who predate the formation of the RI), and ongoing revision of data policies as best practices mature.

Figure 1: Heatmap showing state of Policies for Interoperability

4.1.2 Special Case Legal Policies

Discussion and the state of data policy implementation concerning the major ‘legal’ policies – terms and conditions, liability, cookies, and privacy (especially personal data privacy), are covered in D4.3, including URLs for each policy; a summary heatmap is shown in Figure 2. Colours indicate state of policy element: green=yes, yellow=in progress/partial, red=no. "No"(red) is not always a lack of addressing the policy, sometimes it reflects a different decision by the RI; “in progress/partial” (yellow) is usually a function of the state of development of the RI overall. Note that almost all RI’s have adopted full “legal” data policies, including terms and conditions, liability, cookies, and privacy policies, and have implemented pop-up consent forms (predominance of green). Status for EuroARGO is updated here from that of D4.3 as they have recently finished updating their policies (see Table 28).

Figure 2: Heatmap showing state of “legal” Policies

5 Appendices

5.1 Information package shared with each interview target (including questions)

Email Request

Dear (*RI name*) Colleagues,

I am writing to you about your RI's data policies in the context of ENVRI FAIR and am asking you to update your answers to this questionnaire:

(link to spreadsheet in Google Drive which contained the Policy Questionnaire questions and 2020 answers from that specific RI)

(answer to the right of the shaded area, and also please clarify if you have consent pop-ups for the security features in red).

As part of ENVRI FAIR's WP4 Policy team, I am working with RIs to take stock of their current policies, identify gaps, and facilitate any further work necessary. This process was started with a survey in 2020 led by Ari Asmi, the results of which were included in D4.2 (<https://zenodo.org/record/3961475#.Y9FqQHbMKM8>). You completed the survey at that time, but given that we are all much further down the road, we are asking you to update the questionnaire. I know you have been busy updating your FIP's, and hope that that process now makes this a fairly quick request to answer. This is the basis of D4.5, which I am trying to wrap up this month, so I appreciate your attention to this.

I am looking forward to hearing from you, and I'm very happy to work through this in whatever way helps - don't hesitate to be in touch. I am available all next week from 15:00-16:00 CEST, and at other times if that doesn't work for you - just let me know.

Best regards, MB

Mairi M.R. Best, B.Sc., Ph.D.

Senior Consultant

+1-705-988-3428

m mrbest@gmail.com

Nothing is certain except change... (Heraclitus)

Background:

The ENVRI FAIR 3rd policy workshop (<https://training.envri.eu/course/view.php?id=62>) reviewed some policy components that RIs should consider and provided some examples/templates that may be useful. On slide #20 of the Workshop Presentation, the following are listed as suggested components: Acknowledgement, Authentication, Authorisation, Cookies, Curation, Disaster Recovery, Identifiers, Licensing, Metadata, Physical Security, Privacy, Provenance, Quality Assurance, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and Terms and Conditions - those underlined are particularly important from a legal perspective. This was further confirmed in the 4th policy workshop during ENVRI Week https://iagos-comm.fz-juelich.de/projects/project-meetings/dmsf?folder_id=994, and has influenced the reorganisation of the questionnaire.

Statement within Questionnaire Spreadsheet sent to each RI

The intent of this questionnaire (interview) is to collect information on the existing policy documentation or plans of the infrastructure you represent. Access to the questionnaire results is given to the members of the Policy Working Group of WP4 of ENVRI-FAIR H2020 project. The information is intended to be used to create the policy landscape deliverable of WP4, and to support the work of the Policy working group during project time. The information outside of the deliverable is not published outside of the group. The data is deleted latest by the end of the ENVRI-FAIR project. Only personal information collected is your name (for reference and information checking purposes). This information is not included in the deliverable or published information. The approximate time for this interview is less than

one hour (although depending on the level of information available). You may stop the interview or decline to answer ANY question, without any need to inform reason. Please indicate (YES) if you consent to this use of information you provide.

Policy Questions and Categories

<i>Priority Policies for Interoperability</i>	2020 Questionnaire
<i>Licensing</i>	1. Licence policy: Do you have a chosen licence for your data? If so, which? Are multiple licences applied?
<i>Licensing</i>	1.2. Is the licence also applicable to your metadata? If not, what licence is used for your metadata?
<i>Licensing</i>	1.1. Is the licence machine readable?
<i>Licensing</i>	7. Ownership and rights: Do you have agreement with your data providers (if relevant) on the ownership and licencing of data?
<i>Authorisation/Authentication</i>	6. Data Access: Do you have an access policy for the data?
<i>Authorisation/Authentication</i>	6.1. What are the access formalities for data (or different kinds of data)?
<i>Authorisation/Authentication</i>	6.2. Is there a formal process for accessing restricted data (if relevant)?
<i>Authorisation/Authentication</i>	6.3. Do you allow external authorization (i.e. registration via another trusted source)?
<i>Authorisation/Authentication</i>	6.5. Is the access policy available in machine readable form?
<i>Metadata (FAIR)</i>	4. Metadata: Does your data have included metadata? (are there exceptions ?)
<i>Metadata (FAIR)</i>	4.1 Does your RI's metadata follow some standard(s)?
<i>Metadata (FAIR)</i>	4.2. Does your RI use controlled vocabularies for metadata?
<i>Metadata (FAIR)</i>	4.2.1. Are these vocabularies controlled by your RI?
<i>Metadata (FAIR)</i>	4.3 Does your RI have a policy/practice for quality control of metadata?
<i>Metadata (FAIR)</i>	4.4 Do you share your metadata (i.e. give access to it by outside searches, or share copies for some external service; Is the metadata openly accessible)?
<i>Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement</i>	2. Dataset definition: Do you have a definition of what a dataset is in your RI? This refers to both scientific (i.e. variables involved) and practical (temporal, experiment, etc) separation of each dataset? (data granularity)
<i>Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement</i>	2.1. Do you define a data version? What are the policies/practices (if any) regarding versioning?
<i>Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement</i>	4.5. Do you have a policy on authorship of the data (i.e. which roles are included as authors?)
<i>Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement</i>	6.4. Do you require users to cite or reference to your data if used? If so, do you provide a clear definition of how this should be done?
<i>Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement</i>	3. Persistent identifiers: Do your datasets have PIDs? Are there exceptions?
<i>Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement</i>	3.1 Which PID(s) do you use? Are they internal or external?
<i>Curation</i>	8. Service availability: Does your data service have a service level agreement (or other way to define uptime goals, etc)?
<i>Curation</i>	9. Is there a policy for keeping data and metadata constantly available?
<i>Curation</i>	5. Retention: Do you have a policy for retention of data and metadata?
<i>Curation</i>	5.1. Do you have a described data deletion / reduction process?
<i>Curation</i>	5.2. Do you have a policy/plan for data/metadata availability in the long-run (e.g. closure of the RI)?
<i>General</i>	Policy availability. Generally, do you have the RI policies/practices published in a findable and accessible way? Do they have PIDs?

5.2 Interview results of contributing RIs

Table 1. Category Licensing. Raw answers to the question **Do you have chosen a licence for your data? If so, which? Are multiple licences applied?**

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>1. License Policy: Do you have a chosen licence for your data? If so, which? Are multiple licences applied?</i>
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	CC4.0 (subtype unknown) is intended to be used Universally, and consortium has agreed to use CC, but the details are still pending, (in English, available website) BUT, currently a ad-hoc licence which requires co-authorship (in the data policy)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes only CC-BY 4.0
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Not chosen yet. It has been discussed, some options mapped: CC4.0 BY or similar. Data policy says as little restrictive as possible. As open as possible, as closed as necessary. Try to avoid multiple licensing.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	yes Decision to recommend CCBY4.0 for the 1st ACTRIS GA June 2023
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes CC-BY 4.0. Official policy, universal Except for the raw data (no licence yet), property of the data providers
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	yes Raw data is CC4BY, conditions are a bit different for atmosphere than ecosystem and ocean. A common policy will be prepared for next funding period.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	"Rules of the road" are available for the data download. Internal licence. Official, and practically agreed.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	EISCAT data are the property of the EISCAT Scientific Association. Use is granted according to the EISCAT Statutes (Blue Book) rules. In summary, embargo rules apply to data at low levels for Common Programme (CP) (L1 and L2 data), whereas analysed CP data (L3) are open for use. In the case of Special Programme (SP), the embargo is more prolonged for L1 and L2 data and also applies to analysed (L3) data. Metadata is generally open for use. Users are kindly requested to contact the Association before publishing data and also to add the following Acknowledgement to all publications: 'EISCAT is an international association supported by research organisations in China (CRIRP), Finland (SA), Japan (NIPR), Norway (NFR), Sweden (VR), and the United Kingdom (UKRI)'. Allowed usage of the data is summarised in the Rules of the Road. Data and metadata are stored indefinitely.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	yes Complex. SIOS documentation recommends CC4.0BY, SIOS depends on existing data which can have different licenses. recommendation of any dataset created from SIOS data to have CC4.0BY, but no enforcement.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	yes Complex. SIOS documentation recommends CC4.0BY, SIOS depends on existing data which can have different licenses. recommendation of any dataset created from SIOS data to have CC4.0BY, but no enforcement. The metadata model from SIOS supports a list of CC licenses (including URL resolution), as well as free text (not recommended)
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	no there are several. Open as possible, no concrete license has been agreed. Draft licence was developed. Generally, releases have used CC0 & CC-BY. Central data products will have separate eLTER licence (intention CC0). This will be revised in the current PPP.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	No, there are several depending on the provision of the datasets. For Standard Observation data (SO, core observations of eLTER) within the eLTER PPP project a data policy (D3.3 Data Policy) is defined, which applies to the core eLTER data streams. For eLTER Data Products CC-BY license is applied. "Data are made available under a CC-BY licence with expectation that acknowledgement will be given via the data citation mechanisms of the eLTER RI. Users of eLTER RI data are normally expected to make resulting publications available through open access publications.". D3.3 is still in development and refinement. For historic/legacy eLTER data covering SO different licenses might be applied depending on the data provider. But data should be as open as possible.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Not at moment. But will be selected from the open-source licences. One of the CC licences. Many of the countries participating in LifeWatch have their own policies: Most are CC compliant (CC0 or CC-BY). Some cases include embargo (e.g. campaigns etc.).

RI	Survey	1. License Policy: Do you have a chosen licence for your data? If so, which? Are multiple licences applied?
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	In this moment, in case of data offered by data providers we must follow the same policies and licenses. In case of Data provided by LifeWatch ERIC, if the data has been resulted of the research by a group we encourage the use of CC-BY, in case of data collected automatically we encourage CC-BY. In case of data collected by citizens CC0 need to be selected due to GDPR, the exception is those projects where contributors signed up and allow sharing their personal info, in that case CC-BY could be applied, but not always.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	no explicit choice yet. Community norm on CC licences. Openness & interoperability. "As open as possible, as closed as legally necessary" Majority CC (often CC-BY). MoU required commitment on openness. Software licences: Recommendation permissive licence (MIT, Apache, etc.), not e.g., GPL (although some components might have such licences).
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	no explicit choice yet. Community norm on CC licences. Openness & interoperability. "As open as possible, as closed as legally necessary" Majority CC (often CC-BY). MoU required commitment on openness. Software licences: Recommendation permissive licence (MIT, Apache, etc.), not e.g., GPL (although some components might have such licences).
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	yes Recommended licence CC-BY-SA, but can accept wide range of open data licence. Some platforms require e.g., Italian open data licence. AnaEE makes sure that all these national licences are allowed. Best practice: if not compatible licence with CC-BY, then use double-licences. Clearly stated in the DMP.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	yes Recommended licence CC-BY-SA, but can accept wide range of open data licence. Some platforms require e.g., Italian open data licence. AnaEE makes sure that all these national licences are allowed. Best practice: if not compatible licence with CC-BY, then use double-licences. Clearly stated in the DMP.
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	Yes /CC-BY/yes CC-BY-NC for some assets
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	no licence yet, no decision yet. Discussions (CC mentioned).
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	in progress CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International considered currently in the DMP and DP, historical data should preserve existing licences
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	yes Open and free of data policy. IOC resolution XX-6 Official policy, Agreed on the member state level. Data is free to use but acknowledgement is needed See IOC resolution XX-6: http://argo.jcommops.org/IOC_Resolution_XX-6.html CC-BY licence: https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	<u>yes Open and free of data policy.</u> <u>IOC resolution XX-6 Official policy, Agreed on the member state level. Data is free to use but acknowledgement is needed</u> <u>See :</u> <u>IOC resolution XX-6: http://argo.jcommops.org/IOC_Resolution_XX-6.html</u> <u>CC-BY licence: https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/ applicable on Argo Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC) https://doi.org/10.17882/42182</u>
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes multiple licenses but mainly CC BY 4

Table 2. Category Licensing. Raw answers to the question Is the licence also applicable to your metadata? If not, what licence is used for your metadata?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>1.2. Is the licence also applicable to your metadata? If not, what licence is used for your metadata?</i>
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	no licence for metadata
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	other licence for metadata: CC0 1.0
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Has been discussed, not necessarily the same as for data.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Decision to recommend CCBY4.0 also for meta data at 1st GA
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Most likely. Data in the files has the licence of the data. Includes the author information & affiliation Other metadata is CC0 Not an official policy at the moment.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	Most likely. Data in the files has the licence of the data. Includes the author information & affiliation Other metadata is CC0 Not an official policy at the moment.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	no official, but in practice open metadata
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Not explicitly stated. The metadata is open in practice.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Not specifically. Metadata is thought as open, but licence not really considered yet. WMO has discussions on metadata openness and licensing. For data which has metadata included (NETCDF, etc.) the metadata has the same licence as the data.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Not specifically. Metadata is thought as open, but licence not really considered yet. WMO has discussions on metadata openness and licensing. For data which has metadata included (NETCDF, etc.) the metadata has the same licence as the data.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Open in practice Data policy defines that metadata is freely and openly available.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Metadata (e.g. site information, dataset metadata) are subjected to CC0 being free and open
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	no (in the ERIC level). National hub level metadata is free (even as a policy in some countries, agreed when submitting data).
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	yes Not likely to have different licence of the metadata, as strongly connected to the data, they should have similar licence. Blurry boundary between the two.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	yes Not likely to have different licence of the metadata, as strongly connected to the data, they should have similar licence. Blurry boundary between the two.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Yes official DMP policy mentions that the metadata has the same licence as data.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	Yes official DMP policy mentions that the metadata has the same licence as data.
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes/CC-BY/
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	N/A, same direction of discussion as above (CC).
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International considered currently in the DMP and DP
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	yes Each NetCDF contains data&metadata - metadata is open and free
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	yes Each NetCDF file contains data and metadata Both are open and free
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 3. Category Licensing. Raw answers to the question Is the licence machine-readable?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>1.1. Is the licence machine-readable?</i>
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	included in the metadata, not really Machine-readable
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	N/A, but will be
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	yes
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	no, working on it. Own ontology does not have it, DOI metadata has.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	Yes
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	no
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	No
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	SIOS harvests from existing data repositories. New information model can transfer licence data to users M2M, but not implemented yet. If the data is not there from the existing data centre, this will of course not work.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	See above, we support a list of creative common license using the http://spdx.org/licenses list.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Only by reference to CC templates (not all would have it) Metadata includes data policy reference (but can very heterogeneous, M2M depends on metadata, e.g., data policy reference)
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Only by reference to the CC templates. Metadata for core data products include license information in the metadata, which are referable. This metadata are authored and shared using the Digital Asset Register (DAR), the central data catalogue for eLTER. Machine readability depends on the reference of the license in the metadata, which might differ when metadata for level 0 data are harvested from local data providers. Datasets shared by the eLTER facilities via EUDAT B2SHARE provide license information via the B2SHARE-API.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Once selected, it will be machine-readable, national level exists already some licences which are already machine-readable.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue, allows machine-readable license definition
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	DiSSCo service catalogue has not been yet selected. Specimen records has machine-readable licences associated with the data. This is the vast majority of DiSSCo data assets. Some additional datasets are no on this form. Machine readability is the goal, and the community is well behind this.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	NO There is a metadata element however, not all licences are described the same way. This still requires more training and community uptake
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Yes, CC-BY-SA machine-readable. For national licences, not all are machine-readable, but then there is a link to the licence description.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	Yes, CC-BY-SA machine-readable. For national licences, not all are machine-readable, but then there is a link to the licence description.
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	no
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	N/A
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	N/A
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Yes (CC-BY mentioned in the metadata) Argo (2020). Argo float data and metadata from Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC). SEANOE. https://doi.org/10.17882/42182 The licence is CC-BY https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Yes (CC-BY mentioned in the metadata) Argo float data and metadata from Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC) https://doi.org/10.17882/42182 The licence is CC-BY https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 4. Category Licensing. Raw answers to the question Do you have agreement with your data providers (if relevant) on the ownership and licencing of data?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	7. Ownership and rights: Do you have agreement with your data providers (if relevant) on the ownership and licencing of data?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Ownership and rights are defined in the AISBL statutes. The IAGOS has the licensing rights of this data from there on (with the approved scheme).
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	idem
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Owner is the data originator (by law). Agreement with data originators (mentioned in data policy). Licensing being considered.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Owner is the data originator (by law). Agreement with data originators (mentioned in data policy). Licensing being considered.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes, official policy, by contracts with national networks and thematic centres.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	EISCAT owns the data.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	EISCAT owns the data, and has all connected responsibilities
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	SIOS has no licence for the data. All is owned by the data providers. In the DMP or data policy section on ownership.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	SIOS has no licence for the data. All is owned by the data providers. In the DMP or data policy section on ownership.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	No (when there is a legal entity this will be considered)
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	not at the moment, this will be part of the eLTER RI ERIC. Documents are currently prepared.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	no ownership is claimed for data. We are in the process of defining those licensing agreements. And both aspects will be addressed following best practices applied by European RIs, compulsorily following ENVRI ones ^[P] _[SEP]
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	Still W.I.P.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	DiSSCo consortium will have agreements between the nodes and the hub.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	DiSSCo consortium will have agreements between the nodes and the hub.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Platform or PI owns the data. Each platform should provide description of their licensing policy. Expected to be compatible, but if not, there is ongoing discussions to harmonise the policies (ongoing process).
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes - part of contract (and payment)
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Discussion on this. Ownership is not decided, but most likely preserved on the data providers.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	new data gathered and financed by DANUBIUS-RI are owned by DANUBIUS-RI, otherwise data providers should be preserved, policy included in DMP
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Network requires the data becomes "ARGO data", ownership is given to ARGO. Implicit, and based on IOC resolution.
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Argo data is a public common
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 5. Category Authorisation and Authentication. Raw answers to the question Do you have an access policy for the data?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	6. Data Access: Do you have an access policy for the data?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Written in the procedure during the database registration.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, described in IAGOS data policy: https://iagos.aeris-data.fr/data-policy/
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Yes, access policy exists, separate documents on the (dmp, data access policy, access policy (inc. data)) All policy docs formally agreed.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Yes, access policy exists, separate documents on the (dmp, data access policy, access policy (inc. data)) All policy docs formally agreed.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes, data is certifiably FAIR. This is also the ICOS mission (statutes). All ICOS data is available for free. Anonymously (registration optional). Raw data on request. (under discussion, different approaches internal)
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	"Rules of the road" - including embargo times. Officially agreed.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes. The EISCAT agreement includes a regulated access policy, with embargo rules etc.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Free and open, some services require registration (resource limitation)
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Free and open, some services require registration (resource limitation)
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	For the LTER data products needs to be defined (in PPP). For the datasets provided by the national sites, there is heterogenous processes. Some all free with citation, some require more. no registration for some datasets, some require more authorisation. For the openly shared data no registration, anonymous access.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	For the LTER data products needs to be defined (in PPP). For the datasets provided by the national sites, there is heterogenous processes. Some all free with citation, some require more. no registration for some datasets, some require more authorisation. For the openly shared data no registration, anonymous access.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	AAI + accounting and accountability. Identifying each users for each data. Followup of the users and the data they access. A policy which requires registration and confirmation and access. Authorisation of each user. National level also limitations on the volume of the data.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Everything is based on openness for digital content. No barrier exists. There might be practical reasons (e.g., large data) requiring email address. No actual gatekeeping. At least in practice level now. Coordinated physical access is handled separately in the institutions and being integrated. SYNTHESIS access policy development.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Everything is based on openness for digital content. No barrier exists. There might be practical reasons (e.g., large data) requiring email address. No actual gatekeeping. At least in practice level now. Coordinated physical access is handled separately in the institutions and being integrated. SYNTHESIS access policy development.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Anyone can access. Registration is optional. APIs require registration (resource limitation). (data under revision is confidential only to actors, curators, reviewers) Official in DMP.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Authorisation is required (eduGAIN). User strategy document requires registration for monitoring and feedback reasons. There is an access policy draft.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	Issue has been addressed; access policy is included in DMP
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Everyone can access, commercial, anonymous. Official ARGO policy. No right to do statistics of individual users.
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	The Argo data are free unrestricted access, with a CC-BY license. Argo data policy does not allow to track individual (or other) users.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 6. Category Authorisation and Authentication Raw answers to the question *What are the access formalities for data (or different kinds of data)?*

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	6.1. What are the access formalities for data (or different kinds of data)?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	a PI will evaluate the application for access. The access is then provided by the database manager. The process is described on the website transparently (not machine readably). Agreed practice, but not actual policy of IAGOS (but could be in a GA note etc.). Could be also answered in DMP
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	a PI will evaluate the application for access. The access is then provided by the database manager. described in the DMP
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Depends, ACTRIS Data (lv2) free, anonymous, other levels are controlled. Specific tools, services have their own specific policies.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Depends, ACTRIS Data (QA and NRT -> lv2 and lv1) free, anonymous, other levels are controlled. Specific tools, services have their own specific policies.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	End results are anonymously freely available. (CC4.0 BY) Raw data licence is not clear yet, under discussion. Raw data access is unknown (contact PI currently). Metadata available of course.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Openly available, anonymous, but should follow the "rules of the road"
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	High level data are openly available, but its usage should obey the "rule of the road" as stated on the portal.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Data No formalities, for services: the registration is up to SIOS data centre (to determine real users). Currently no authorisation to data.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	There are no formalities for accessing data. For accessing services registration is needed. SIOS has implemented SSO solutions, but a access is given after human checks.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Vary
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	still multiple
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Apply for access (depending on the data type and volume). LifeWatch decides access.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020, but W.I.P on standardise by default policies through EOSC and other projects and R.I.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	None
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	None
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Most data no formalities. Only for reviewing, API development versions etc., one needs to apply.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	login
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	no review process is yet considered
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	discussions are running on this matter, no decision yet
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	No formalities (just go on the website).
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	No formality, the data is online.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Based on ERDDAP

Table 7. Category Authorisation and Authentication. Raw answers to the question *Is there a formal process for accessing restricted data (if relevant)?*

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	6.2. Is there a formal process for accessing restricted data (if relevant)?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	n/a
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	n/a
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Data centre(s) will give access to users on request
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Data centre(s) will give access to users on request to Head Office- SAMU
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes (informal), raw data is asked to contact the PI. (ICOS does not have the licence for raw data)
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Raw is restricted. Policy is being considered.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Access to low level data is restricted based on the affiliation country of the user and experimenter.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	No restricted data (restricted data is not in the catalogue), information model could handle it (including restricted metadata), not implemented yet.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	There is no restricted data (restricted data is not in the catalogue). The SIOS information model could anyway handle it (including restricted metadata), not implemented yet.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Multiple ways.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	multiple ways, currently no restricted data for eLTER
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	No, a practice.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	These should be handled in the national/institutional level, details to be developed.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Some of these will be implemented in the digital specimen level. Rest will be handled by the national/institution level. Some coordination will require from DiSSCo
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	No restricted data (outside revision cycle).
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	we are working on the AAI; some asset suppliers have this in place linked to the central catalog
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	NO. There will be some restricted data (user categories, resource limited data products). Embargoed data may be in the data portal (for a limited data). The process has not been created.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	No restricted data, even non-standardised data must be shared. As part of the IOC resolution XX-6 countries can ask to stop data transmission of the Central portal when a float is collecting information in their EEZ. This has never happened in past 20 years.
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Not relevant, there is no restricted data. An Argo float has nothing to hide: it is mandatory to publish in real-time and delayed mode any observation from an Argo float.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	N/A

Table 8. Category Authorisation and Authentication. Raw answers to the question Do you allow external authorisation (i.e., registration via another trusted source)?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	6.3. Do you allow external authorisation (i.e., registration via another trusted source)?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Not right now, but soon will be able to use ORCID & eduGAIN access is allowed (technical level might need clarification)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, ORCID and eduGAIN
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	This is under discussion/implementation (options exist), a part of FAIRness implementation plan in ENVRI-FAIR.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	not now
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	ORCID, eduGAIN, (Facebook) CarbonPortal, OBSpack via NOAA
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	For the low-level data this is being considered.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, EGI-checkin has been established as authentication service for low level data.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Not needed as now but has been considered. (ENVRI-FAIR solutions has not been concrete enough yet).
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Authorisation is not need for accessing data, nor authentication. See above, SSO has been implemented for authentication to access extra services or internal pages.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	No. But probably considered in the future
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	No, but considered for the future
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	no, but under development (in ENVRI-FAIR etc.)
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	Yes, W.I.P. (e.g., EOSC, EGI, ...)
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Some services need authorisation for workflow needs, e.g., for requiring physical access, or digitalisation on-demand. SYNTHESIS is building ORCID/eduGAIN based system.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	We have implemented AAI for two of our services that supports open protocols.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Federated access across the AnaEE platforms, Plans on federation in ENVRI. Infrastructure already there.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	external authentication but local authorisation
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	eduGAIN is considered to be used.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	eduGAIN included in DMP, other auth methods are considered
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	no
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Not applicable
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 9. Category Authorisation and Authentication. Raw answers to the question Is the access policy available in machine-readable form?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>6.5. Is the access policy available in machine-readable form?</i>
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	No
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	no
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Will come with licensing.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Will come with licensing.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	CC4.0 BY mentioned in the metadata, included in the landing page.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	(not Machine-readable)-
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	No
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	no not really.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	No
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	no
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	not at the moment
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	no (sometimes licences are in the metadata). Most of the data provided with the CC licence.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	Not at this moment but W.I.P. to allow it in the future
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	It is possible but not implemented.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Work in progress
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Metadata includes must include at least one citable item as reference.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes (document)
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	N/A
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	yes, see above
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Yes, CC-BY https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	N/A

Table 10. Category Metadata. Raw answers to the question Does your data have included metadata? (are there exceptions?)

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4. Metadata: Does your data have included metadata? (are there exceptions ?)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Yes, policy status unknown but likely. In practice but will be included in the DMP for policy. Responsible: Data centre adds the metadata.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, all data in NetCDF format including metadata
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Yes, all ACTRIS Data has metadata included. Generally included by the producers at the sites. (chambers?)
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Yes, all ACTRIS Data has metadata included. Generally included by the producers at the sites. (chambers?)
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes. L0 metadata from PI, L1 metadata from Thematic centres, L2 from carbon portal. Official policy. Metadata profile for each data object type + ontology information. Data policy is most likely being updated (raw data) in some time relatively soon.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	yes, Note that our data and metadata are intertwined; the PIDs point to the metadata (collected as human- and machine-readable landing pages". When people download datasets, they are (in most cases) also provided with a URL pointing to the data object's landing page.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	yes, Metadata is included for all data. Mainly automatic, some manual adjustments needed (e.g., authorship), done by the EISCAT data centre.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, metadata is included for all data. It is mainly done automatically, but some manual adjustments may be needed by the EISCAT data centre.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Depends on the data. Guidelines are being developed. Ambition is to harmonise the SIOS core data, but the generally there are many data sources outside of it, with differing metadata. SIOS will only harvest the metadata provided by the sources and transform it to SIOS metadata model (only for the discovery metadata).
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Depends on the data. Guidelines are being developed. Ambition is to harmonise the SIOS core data, but the generally there are many data sources outside of it, with differing metadata. SIOS will only harvest the metadata provided by the sources and transform it to SIOS metadata model (only for the discovery metadata).
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Yes, there is a policy. At least the central catalogue provided data will need to have metadata. Data is provided both centrally and on the local level. Landing pages of the DOIs are not controlled by the eLTER, and not part of the catalogue. B2SHARE includes LTER template, with reference to more descriptive metadata recording the eLTER catalogue.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Yes, SO datasets and data products have to be documented in the Digital Asset Register (DAR) including provenance. Historic/legacy SO data (level 0) are shared and documented either using EUDAT B2SHARE (DOI minted) or in local data management systems, which needs to expose standard compliant and FAIR metadata. These references will be used for tracking the provenance. This feature is still under development.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Yes, official policy. Task force on metadata. Annotated metadata. Corresponding catalogues. (1) Definition and implementation of good practices associated to metadata, controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, and semantics in general terms.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Yes, official policy and key requirement for your operations. Originates from the national/institutional level, required to follow standards (see below)
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Yes, Our data and metadata are the same for the specimen records.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Yes, part of DMP. no exceptions.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4. Metadata: Does your data have included metadata? (are there exceptions ?)
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	some communities have included metadata but still provide external metadata for the catalog
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Yes, this is required for new (DANUBIUS) data
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	yes, Mandatory for new data, for historical data at this moment there is proposed to generate/build associated metadata
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	NetCDF has included metadata. National data centres create the metadata, transferred on the International Argo Data Central portals (For security reasons there are 2 central portals one in USA one in France that synchronise their data holding every hour)
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Argo data and metadata are managed in NetCDF files. National Data Assembly Centres (DAC) create the metadata delivered on the Argo Global Data Assembly Centre (GDAC) (For security reasons there are 2 GDACs one in USA one in France that synchronise their data holding every hour)
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 11. Category Metadata. Raw answers to the question 4.1 Does your RI's metadata follow some standard(s)?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>4.1 Does your RI's metadata follow some standard(s)?</i>
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	yes, ISO standards (19115), also WMO standards being implemented. no DMP at the moment (in preparation). Metadata provided will depend on the user group (e.g., WMO will get WMO compliant MD).
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, metadata harvestable by CSW and provided in ISO19115 (ISO 19139 implementation) also DataCite format
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Partly agreed. DMP has includes a list of metadata standards, different standards for different kinds of products. Core metadata will be the same.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Partly agreed. DMP has includes a list of metadata standards, different standards for different kinds of products. Core metadata will be the same.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	W3C, own standard mapped to required metadata standards.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Madrigal standard (for the data which is published there).
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	EISCAT data follow the Madrigal standard for the data that is published there.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Recommendation CF convention, ACDD - for NETCDF Darwin core archive for biodiversity data (lots of other data as well) INSPIRE directive. Data policy refers to European legislation. Same in the data management plan.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Recommendation CF convention, ACDD - for NETCDF Darwin core archive for biodiversity data (lots of other data as well) INSPIRE directive. Data policy refers to European legislation. Same in the data management plan.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Based on the ISO, internal standard is an evolution. Local metadata model, wide range of information. This is mapped to ISO19115 (INSPIRE), EML. Metadata elements were combined from both. Intention for harvesting the standards. There will a revision of the metadata model in the PPP but will be still available in many flavours in the API. Community profiles will define the core set and will be refined in the current PPP.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Based on the ISO, internal standard is an evolution. Local metadata model, wide range of information. This is mapped to ISO19115 (INSPIRE), EML. Metadata elements were combined from both. Intention for harvesting the standards. There will a revision of the metadata model in the PPP but will be still available in many flavours in the API. Community profiles will define the core set and will be refined in the current PPP.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Yes, best practices for metadata (2) Collecting, Analysing and Opening-up existing standards, and then proposing a set of own standards which may be agreed with different ENVRI Communities-of-Practice (CoPs). EML, Darwin core, INSPIRE, ...
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	same as 2020 The metadata standard currently used to represent datasets on the LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue is a subset of the EML2.2.0 but also ISO19139 representations are allowed.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Darwin Core ABCD (access to biological collection data) ABCDEFG (extension for geology) Other geographical, etc. additional standards Well a developed practice in the field. Work to do: minimum information for collections & specimen standard, formalisation being done in DiSSCo

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>4.1 Does your RI's metadata follow some standard(s)?</i>
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	yes Darwin Core ABCD (access to biological collection data) ABCDEFG (extension for geology) Other geographical, etc. additional standards We have implemented the first version openDS (open digital specimen specification) to harmonise similar terms from different standards and sources.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	ISO metadata (INSPIRE) - expected principle Platforms is given a broad range to fulfil the metadata. But in the end of revision cycle, the internal & external interoperability is assessed. Some criteria harder than others.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	there are >17 different metadata standards in the asset suppliers. These are converted to EPOS-DCAT-AP and thence to CERIF in the catalogue
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	There is a principle of metadata model, but not implemented. INSPIRE. Heterogenous sources. ISO standards 19115, EML standards. OpenAire standards. A final set of potential candidates have been prepared. Also discussed with representatives with other RIs from the ENVRI cluster.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Yes, all developments are shared in the ENVRI-FAIR. The metadata are documented in "Argo User's manual" http://dx.doi.org/10.13155/29825 This document is published on Ocean Best Practices https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	yes, Argo metadata are documented in "Argo User's manual" http://dx.doi.org/10.13155/29825 This document is published on Ocean Best Practices https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/ Argo metadata is based on vocabularies published in the Argo vocabulary server.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 12. Category Metadata. Raw answers to the question Does your RI use-controlled vocabularies for metadata?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4.2. Does your RI use-controlled vocabularies for metadata?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	CF convention for metadata, GCMD (global common... NASA). Practical AERIS decision. Can change in future.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	CF standard name for variables GCMD for variables, instruments, and platforms
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	CF is used, apply new terms if missing. Some have internal vocabulary. Same across all centres.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	yes https://vocabulary.actris.nilu.no/skosmos/actris_vocab/en/
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes, own controlled vocabularies (ontology is one), not follow ISO11759(?). Content agreed internally with thematic centres. NetCDF files follow CF conventions (not INSPIRE actually)
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Yes, Madrigal
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	<u>Yes, it is using Madrigal. In addition, the ontology prepared by the HORIZON 2020 PITHIA-NRF project will be used in the future. It is in turn based on the ESPAS FP7 ontology.</u>
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Discovery metadata: OSGEO URL purpose CF standard names GBIF keywords For use metadata, depends on the data source (usually NO).
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Discovery metadata: OSGEO URL purpose CF standard names GBIF keywords, GCMD Keywords. For use metadata, depends on the data source (usually NO).
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Yes Recommendation to use ENVTHES, but no enforcement.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Yes Recommendation to use ENVTHES, but no enforcement.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Yes, semantics, general terms.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Yes. Multiple are required in the standards definitions. Describing the changing names of species.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Yes, but we are not using a vocabulary server or service yet. There are a few existing one in the community that we would like to extend and re-use. This required adding several new terms and maintaining them.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	AnaEE thesaurus - more detailed and tracks provenance and categorises the data Core presentation metadata - required minimum
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes, many
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Not selected yet, but DMP will require some set of common vocabularies.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	NVS NERC Vocabulary Service considered for the next version of DMP
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Yes, own vocabularies (Argo-specific, but links with existing vocabularies, using existing if possible) They contain subsets of CF standard names. SeaDataNet vocabularies as well used.
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Yes, Argo metadata use-controlled vocabularies. The Argo vocabularies (R tables) are published on NVS vocabulary server http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/search_nvs/ Smart mappings between Argo vocabularies (R* tables) and other major vocabularies address cross domain activities.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 14. Category Metadata. Raw answers to the question Does your RI have a policy/practice for quality control of metadata?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4.3 Does your RI have a policy/practice for quality control of metadata?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	no for the metadata
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	no
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Quality control in the data centre. Automatic, and manual. Legacy data has less strict format (MD quality can vary there)
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Yes Quality control in the data centre. Automatic, and manual. Legacy data has less strict format (MD quality can vary there)
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	yes, Levels progression & labeling has some level of QC for observation data. Consistency is checked automatically in the ingestion. Metadata concerning the stations regularly reviewed between HO and stations for the ICOS Handbook.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Not really
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	no This has not been implemented.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	yes, Discovery metadata. Not a policy, but in practice there is a quality check, (strict), title abstract, temporal duration, station, etc. Use metadata no check (currently). CF compliance (subset) required for some services.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	yes, Discovery metadata. Not a policy, but in practice there is a quality check, (strict), title abstract, temporal duration, station, etc. Use metadata no check (currently). CF compliance (subset) required for some services.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Main QC is from the campaigns, for integration in the DEIMS. There is a legacy of metadata not being QC. Catalogue still has such metadata. DEIMS only checks completeness. no content quality check. DEIMS is the historic catalogue (not only eLTER). The subset of eLTER might need to be separately considered. Policies would then be different for the eLTER only products than to the whole DEIMS. Policy being considered. Long-term vision being considered for the eLTER level. Site descriptions is more a practice. There are update cycles, data centre will check this metadata QC. "As inclusive as possible", policies must reflect this.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	in progress Policy for quality control of metadata still needs to be implemented. For DEIMS-SDR, the catalogue to describe the physical assets of the RI (sites, locations, sensors) basic quality control is implemented (https://qa.deims.org/), which allows the user to check the content. Basic content evaluation (e.g., descriptions) is done campaign based and also by supporting the user community. For the Digital Asset Register (DAR), describing the digital assets of the RI (dataset, data product, code) a quality control process is considered and will be implemented in the upcoming months. This will also include training of users and data providers. For historic/legacy data (level 0) quality check of metadata is under the responsibility of the data provider.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	This metadata task force has a periodical review control quarterly. LifeWatch has benchmarking process for external sources and internal processes. Official practice (will be policy when agreed in the General Assembly) - one of the WGs is working on the metadata. based ion the collected best practices.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	We need to improve the quality process I would add but with the new version of the Metadata Catalogue, which will be released within 2023, there will be review workflows and other automatic quality control mechanisms.

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4.3 Does your RI have a policy/practice for quality control of metadata?
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Standards conformity will be most probably done in the DiSSCo level. For some partner organisations (GBIF, etc.) have this already implemented. Content quality are being considered in the community projects, which could be additional services provided by DiSSCo. This is uncertain and will require discussion with the data providers. Also access to original (meta)data is going to be needed. These are community practices, but not on the policy level.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	We have made progress in MIDS (Minimum Information about a Digital Specimen) and current implementation usages this guideline. But no proper quality control policies yet.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Yes, revision cycle is defined in the DMP. (Peer review of data/metadata, supported by automated tools).
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes - using SHAPES/SHACL on EPOS-DCAT-AP records
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Yes, there is an approved ingest process. Metadata is required and complete. There will be a metadata QC from the data provider, verified in the ingest process (on/off), i.e., second level QM in the data centre to make sure they match the DANUBIUS requirements.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Yes, the international data centre does metadata QC. Official agreement
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	yes, Every Argo NetCDF file metadata has to comply with a series of well documented rule (Argo NetCDF format, Argo cookbooks, Argo QC manuals). These rules are systematically checked by Argo file content checker. Noncompliant files are rejected from Argo GDAC.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 15. Category Metadata. Raw answers to the question Do you share your metadata (i.e., give access to it by outside searches, or share copies for some external service; Is the metadata openly accessible)?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4.4 Do you share your metadata (i.e., give access to it by outside searches, or share copies for some external service; Is the metadata openly accessible)?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Yes, openly available. no licence yet. Metadata can be harvested. Catalogue openly available. Policy status not clear, but could be handled in DMP
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, with open licence CC0 - CSW interface through IAGOS catalogue - in NetCDF files
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Accessible (in implementation, but most have working THREDS)
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	yes THREDDS, WIGOS etc.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Handbook is shared for the stations. Stations also have external metadata shared via e.g., WMO GAW, Fluxnet, etc. This leads to harmonisation in field. Observation data metadata is openly harvestable. Linked open data, SPARQL interface.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	yes, anyone can access the full metadata of all our digital objects, under a CC-0 license.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Have been part of projects, not operational at the moment. Could be in the future.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	yes, EISCAT data is/will be part of the ENVRI hub and the PITHIA-NRF e-science centre. The data have also been part of earlier projects.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Not from the SIOS data centre. In theory yes, but the performance now is not usable. But soon available. From the SIOS point of view, it is available as a practice (not policy). Not re-sharing things without appropriate identifiers and without the originator data centres' permission.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	yes, Metadata records are exposed through a M2M endpoint which is openly available.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Yes, available and shared (e.g., GEOSS). Decision made on this on LTER Europe level. https://deims.org/pycsw/csw (CSW GetCapabilities Link) https://deims.org/pycsw/csw.py?mode=oaipmh&verb=Identify (OAI-PMH OpenSearch site) INSPIRE requirements are not fulfilled via eLTER, but via their own catalogue. API interface (https://deims.org/api) https://deims.org/geoserver/ows?service=wms&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities (WMS 1.3.0 GetCapabilities Link) https://deims.org/geoserver/ows?service=wfs&version=2.0.0&request=GetCapabilities (WFS 2.0.0 GetCapabilities Link) to access the information on the sites
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Yes, available and shared (e.g., GEOSS). Decision made on this on LTER Europe level. https://deims.org/pycsw/csw (CSW GetCapabilities Link) https://deims.org/pycsw/csw.py?mode=oaipmh&verb=Identify (OAI-PMH OpenSearch site) INSPIRE requirements are not fulfilled via eLTER, but via their own catalogue. API interface (https://deims.org/api) https://deims.org/geoserver/ows?service=wms&version=1.3.0&request=GetCapabilities (WMS 1.3.0 GetCapabilities Link) https://deims.org/geoserver/ows?service=wfs&version=2.0.0&request=GetCapabilities (WFS 2.0.0 GetCapabilities Link) to access the information on the sites DAR????
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Yes, they will be available by following an open access policy by default, but implementing proper embargo periods (few cases for e.g., endangered species). ^[15] Practice
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Part of the expectation of DiSSCo, Machine & human accessible. There can be some of the metadata is not available from the institution level for security etc. reasons. (example: rhino horns). Basic premise is that the partners share their collection information: some are not mentioned e.g., from legal etc. reasons. There is no community unified exception list but could be a future DiSSCo activity.

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>4.4 Do you share your metadata (i.e., give access to it by outside searches, or share copies for some external service; Is the metadata openly accessible)?</i>
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	The metadata is accessible, trying to create as much as possible machine-readable. Core metadata is well machine actionable. The metadata is open to external searches.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes, via the EPOS ICS-C Portal
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Proposed in the DMP to be available to everyone (no decision yet). Metadata catalogue in the data portal.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	in progress GeoNetwork and CKAN are considered, and we are planning for OpenAire, DANUBIUS - RI demonstrator in the works
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Openly available via central node.
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Yes, all NetCDF files are online, they contain all metadata. Within ENVRI-FAIR, EuroARGO established a sparql endpoint service to perform semantic queries on Argo metadata
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 16. Category Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement. Raw answers to the question Do you have a definition of what a dataset is in your RI? This refers to both scientific (i.e., variables involved) and practical (temporal, experiment, etc) separation of each dataset? (data granularity)

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	2. Dataset definition: Do you have a definition of what a dataset is in your RI? This refers to both scientific (i.e., variables involved) and practical (temporal, experiment, etc.) separation of each dataset? (data granularity)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	no written definition. Data levels are defined. List of datasets exists (some are subsets of others). Practical: Variety internal practical standards for different purposes. Documented in the data portal. included in the metadata. Will be answered in the DMP (first version probably end of 2020)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes definition of the processing levels: https://iagos.aeris-data.fr/levels/ definition of the products in the IAGOS metadata catalogue: https://iagos.aeris-data.fr/catalogue/ and in DMP: https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/iagos_dmp_v1
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Definition exists, included in the data management plan (see doc). Clear definition of each data type.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Definition exists, included in the data management plan (see doc). Clear definition of each data type.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes, Data objects and data collection, both have a PID. Well defined in documentation and ontology. (document not remembered.) "ICOS Data " well documented. But there are pre-ICOS data & project data. which does not follow the same standards.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	Yes, Data objects and data collection, both have a PID. Well defined in documentation and ontology. (document not remembered..) "ICOS Data " well documented. But there are pre-ICOS data & project data. which does not follow the same standards. See our latest data lifecycle document at https://doi.org/10.18160/D2JV-KB6B
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Yes, definition exists: Experiment. Practical agreement
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, the definition of what a dataset is exists. One experiment is one dataset.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	no strict definition, but it is discussed. Data policy has a definition of dataset (weak). Discussion on "user oriented" definition of dataset instead of "data producer oriented", Data set: A SIOS data set is a discrete collection of scientific data, museum objects or samples which can be described by metadata, compliant to the SIOS data policy, and related to scientific efforts in and around Svalbard within the SIOS framework. ^[P] _[SEP] https://sios-svalbard.org/sites/sios-svalbard.org/files/common/SIOS_Data_Policy.pdf
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	no strict definition, but it is discussed. Data policy has a definition of dataset (weak). Discussion on "user oriented" definition of dataset instead of "data producer oriented", Data set: A SIOS data set is a discrete collection of scientific data, museum objects or samples which can be described by metadata, compliant to the SIOS data policy, and related to scientific efforts in and around Svalbard within the SIOS framework. ^[P] _[SEP] https://sios-svalbard.org/sites/sios-svalbard.org/files/common/SIOS_Data_Policy.pdf
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Formal data set does not exist. Practical solutions are being developed in the PPP. Likely particular set of measurements in temporal / spatial space.

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	2. Dataset definition: Do you have a definition of what a dataset is in your RI? This refers to both scientific (i.e., variables involved) and practical (temporal, experiment, etc.) separation of each dataset? (data granularity)
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	This is currently defined in the eLTER PLUS and PPP project and formalised. Currently, data processing levels (raw data - 0 - 1 - 2 - 3) are defined for the 'data products' delivered by eLTER. The thematic scope and temporal/spatial resolution is defined by the Standard Observations (SO, eLTER PLUS deliverable D3.1, Zacharias et al. 2021). Dataset, as collection of measurements within a temporal and spatial space, are defined based on the SO. Elaborated and derived data products are currently under development.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Not formally decided but depends on the nature of the data collected. Multidimensional, space, variables, taxonomies, data type (real time, etc.). National hub level there are some definitions, and on treatments, etc. Partially solved in the national level and will be used to prepare the LifeWatch level policy.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	Work in Progress through LifeBlock and Metadata Catalogue, but not for all the cases identified in 2020. LUPO (LifeWatch ERIC Upper Ontology) definition of dataset: A set or collection of data, records or information that constitutes distinct units of information in the knowledge generation process.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Yes, primary digital asset (digital specimen). Publication connected. Datasets will be varied, but the primary assets are the specimens. There will be other products with varying dataset definitions in future. Policy or policy type document. Exchange standard on this. Well defined.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Yes, Our primary digital asset is digital specimen. These re individual specimen records and related links, so technically datasets can be composed based on these
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Dataset definition exists, in the DMP: "Datasets are the central objects of AnaEE Data Management Policy: they are self-contained sets of information that include data and all the metadata required to re-use that data. Examples of dataset are: a database of historical and georeferenced observations, an archive of field observation, an archive of laboratory analysis results, a set of field or laboratory images, a set of system logs. A project dataset is composed by the "Foreground Data" and the "Background Data" over the project period." Self contained set e.g., on one experiment one dataset. Full replicability on the data (inc. all background data included).
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates. However, being a working definition, it may be changed over time
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	We have datasets and data products. The latter are processed (to some extent) dataset(s). The datasets are described in the metadata.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Heterogeneous datasets, from many sources. observation data, monitoring, remote sensing etc. Each will require their won decision. Data types (being developed): By Collection method By structure By format
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	By platform, WMO number, trajectory, metadata. One float time series is a dataset. EuroARGO is developing other PID solutions for higher resolutions (Cyle and Variable) to facilitate traceability (activity within ENVRI-FAIR Task Force 3)
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	The Argo dataset is a collection of individual Argo float NetCDF files. For each Argo float, there is a collection of NetCDF metadata file, trajectory file, technical file and vertical profile files (one per individual profile). Within ENVRI-FAIR project, EuroARGO developed data services to access data by geospatial, temporal and EOv criteria.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 17. Category Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement. Raw answers to the question Do you define a data version? What are the policies/practices (if any) regarding versioning?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	2.1. Do you define a data version? What are the policies/practices (if any) regarding versioning?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Versioning procedure is documented. The PID stays constant even if the version different. Provenance system being developed, which will improve the versioning and documentation of it. This will also include more detailed PID system to track data versions.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	we keep all versions when data or metadata change for a file a new PID (handle ePIC) is assigned to a new version
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Versioning exists, there is way to keep track of data, old versions are stored. Has been agreed and implemented in most units (at least).
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Versioning exists, there is way to keep track of data, old versions are stored. Has been agreed and implemented in most units (at least).
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Levels exists, (Raw, L1, L2). Full versioning for all data. Landing page has link to other versions. It is machine-readable. Gap filling. Reprocessing can lead to new versions, mentioned in the metadata. Thematic centres responsible.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Two levels of data (preliminary and final), both are published (preliminary will be replaced by final).
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, there are two versions of the data produced (preliminary and final). The final version is replacing the preliminary one.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Encourage data versioning, but no policy or enforcement. no single way of expressing this to users. Recommend to data centres a new identifier for new. versions, but not always followed.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Encourage data versioning, but no policy or enforcement. no single way of expressing this to users. Recommend to data centres a new identifier for new. versions, but not always followed.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Not centrally. Individual national networks have their own practices. Versioning will be developed for the eLTER level products.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Currently, not for the central data node. This is still in development. The eLTER Central Data Node (CDN) will include versioning for the eLTER SO datasets and data products. For EUDAT B2SHARE which is used to share eLTER facility historic/legacy data, versioning of data records is implemented.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	As above. Some fields crucial for the LifeWatch. Identifying the best practices from the national level hubs. LifeBlock blockchain will be used to help the traceability and versioning and origin of the data. General assembly agreed the prototype and encouraged to implement. (also collaborating with DISSCO and GBIF, probably others, e.g. ICOS). The technology chosen will guarantee implementation of a policy.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	As mentioned in 2020 we are now in the process of deploying LifeBlock
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Digital specimen design includes versioning policies (including ways to follow earlier snapshots). PID points to latest versions. Some providers are versioning aggregated datasets. Not a single unified policy, but well advanced in many data providers. This will be unified in the DiSSCo. Central requirement for us. Some do this via DOIs.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Our current implementation includes version. We display the original data, but any changes get a new version. However, the PID stays the same and resolves to the newest record.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Yes, two policies: Datasets from experiments (spot datasets, foreground datasets) should not require versions, but there is a way to have dataset revision. Revision must be re-started for each new version (including the metadata). Exceptional case, but there is process. For continuous observations: There is a continuous revision cycle. New PID for new version. All versions stay in the system (Git). Metadata is also versioned.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes, different versions have different PIDs, and they are related by semantically rich links
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Data levels are being discussed, will be finalised the DMP. Versioning will be also discussed in the DMP, no solutions implemented yet.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no solution implemented yet, considered for the next version of DMP
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Monthly snapshots of the whole datacenter with each have their DOI. Previous Monthly version can be returned with. History of the processing step available in the NetCDF Files in the History section
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	A monthly snapshot of the whole Argo dataset is archived and accessible online with its specific DOI. Within each NetCDF file, an history of every change and processing steps in data or metadata is recorded.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on a common approach

Table 18. Category Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement. Raw answers to the question Do you have a policy on authorship of the data (i.e., which roles are included as authors?)

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4.5. Do you have a policy on authorship of the data (i.e., which roles are included as authors?)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Yes, metadata has PIs included (all RI connected personnel - especially 2 first are important). Mapping between and ISO and DataCite. AERIS is included as an author. DMP will fix this in a formal way.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	idem
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Contributors select data originators. Attribution given to originator.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	yes, Contributors select data originators. Attribution given to originator.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	yes, there is a policy on this. PI (complicated) + Sponsor (organisation). no indication for RI curation work. Roles are defined, roles define the citation string.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	"EISCAT" is the author. "PI" is Ingemar (almost all data)
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	yes, EISCAT is owner of all the data produced. "PI" of most of the data is Ingemar Häggström.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Comes from the data centres. Depends on the contributing data centre. Current data model has changed the way to theoretically connect persons to data sets. no contributions from the data centres yet though. Information model has room for data centre role (not much used).
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	yes, comes from the data centres, thus depends on the contributing data centre to assign roles for the exposed records. The SIOS metadata model has controlled vocabularies for personnel role including principal investigators, metadata author, technical contact, data center contact. If DOI info is provided, the list of authors is also exposed.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	no but the standard would be DataCite data authorship template. But not decided for the eLTER level data. For the cite provided data is defined by the data providers. Some recommendations exist from the earlier projects.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	yes, draft data policy available, which still needs to be approved by the Interim Council (IC). This states "It is important for the eLTER RI and its Data Users to acknowledge the people and organisations that have originally generated the eLTER Data or processed the different levels of eLTER Data. For this purpose, a persistent identifier with the information of the Data Providers/authors will be accompanied with every eLTER Data set, together with clear information about how to properly acknowledge the eLTER community in the products that make use of eLTER Data. The data originators are responsible for identifying who should receive attribution for each dataset." Regarding authorship of data (including roles) this needs to be further developed in the PPP project.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	in progress LifeWatch is not a exclusively data providing RI, but a mostly modelling and an analysis and annotated RI. New data is created also from the LifeWatch modelling, with author LifeWatch. Authorship is mentioned in the followed metadata standards. LifeBlock will be able to follow the original data and the authors in it (provenance information). Practice.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Authorship chain. political level: institution. Data originators are available as well in the metadata. Attribution information is acknowledged problem. no real community solution yet, extremely complex and heterogeneous situation. Work in progress. Promoting use of ORCIDs, especially for collectors. Provenance is a large part of the digital object model, which could be a major part of such process.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Authorship chain. political level: institution. Data originators are available as well in the metadata. Attribution information is acknowledged problem. no real community solution yet, extremely complex and heterogeneous situation. Work in progress Promoting use of ORCIDs, especially for collectors. Provenance is a large part of the digital object model, which could be a major part of such process.

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	4.5. Do you have a policy on authorship of the data (i.e., which roles are included as authors?)
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Complicated. Revision process requires owner & curators. These are coming from the research platforms.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes, we record persons with their roles
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Datasets must have identifiers, which need to include information on the authors. no policy on the RI level (but data provider will provide). Data should include information on the data originator. But there is no decision yet.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	yes, this policy has been included in DP, approved by DANUBIUS BGR
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Different levels, Authors are included from PI level to data centre personnel. Who-has-been-doing-what. Institution vocabulary. Mentioned in the user manual (official document). The Argo dataset DOI list its 250 contributors (preferably with their ORCID), see https://doi.org/10.17882/42182
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	yes The Argo GDAC DOI author is a community of authors: "Argo" The Argo GDAC DOI lists more than 250 individual contributors (preferably with their ORCID), see https://doi.org/10.17882/42182 Contributors are scientific PIs, data managers, engineers, etc. The scientific that performed the delayed mode QC are recorded in the NetCDF files with their ORCID personal PID.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on a common approach

Table 19. Category Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement. Raw answers to the question Do you require users to cite or reference to your data if used? If so, do you provide a clear definition of how this should be done?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	6.4. Do you require users to cite or reference to your data if used? If so, do you provide a clear definition of how this should be done?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Registration requires approval of data protocol, including the citation requirements and co-authorship is required for major data use. Official policy
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, in data policy
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	There is a need to cite. They are provided information to contact the data originator. This will change to DOI and attribution information in the landing page.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	There is a need to cite. They are provided information to contact the data originator and DOI implementation is in the final stage. Attribution information in the landing page.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	This is part of the data policy. Instructions are given directly when downloading. M2M also includes a step for confirming the acknowledgement requirements. One can also set this on personal settings (not asking after that). DOI has URL to CC-BY
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Acknowledgement is needed. Example is given.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, an acknowledgement is required. An example text is provided.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Recommended, but not really a policy. New data model should include necessary data This is not visible in the portal, but "from data management plan: Users of data supplied through SIOS shall acknowledge in any publication or any other derived work, the contribution made by those who have created and worked up the data. If the data licence does not specify how best to do this, data should be formally cited using the citation text provided on the dataset's landing page or in its metadata. Those who retrieve data through SIOS shall acknowledge SIOS as follows: Contains data retrieved through SIOS (year) ^{1,2,3,4} " (probably changing very soon)
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Recommended, but not really a policy. On the https://sios-svalbard.org/metsis/search Citation of data and services" guidelines are given as stated in the data policy document: "Users of data supplied through SIOS shall acknowledge in any publication or any other derived work, the contribution made by those who have created and worked up the data. If the data licence does not specify how best to do this, data should be formally cited using the citation text provided on the dataset's landing page or in its metadata. Those who retrieve data through SIOS shall acknowledge SIOS as follows: Contains data retrieved through SIOS (year)."
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	For some the products (which have DOIs), this is provided. Not true for a lot of other datasets. DEIMS datasets have a recommended citation, for each dataset separately.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Yes, either via the DOI or by citation recommendation. For historic/legacy (level 0) data this is subjected to the data providers.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Depends on the licence which the data is available. CC-BY require a reference. This is practice, that follows from the national data providers policies. Datasets with DOI should be quoted with it. Not communicated to the users in a single way.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Work in progress.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Still work in progress.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Licences CC-BY require this. Definition in the metadata.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes/no - but working on this
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Citation will be required, but the details have not been decided. Recommendations are being drafted.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Yes. Required, but no way of imposing. Example citation provided in the metadata (machine-readable) and in the DOI.
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Yes, there is a citation statement well advertised on Argo GDAC DOI https://doi.org/10.17882/42182
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on improving this issue

Table 20. Category Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement. Raw answers to the question Do your datasets have PIDs? Are there exceptions?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	3. Persistent identifiers: Do your datasets have PIDs? Are there exceptions?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	yes, all datasets have PID. Data center AERIS provides them. Implicit in the AERIS contract that they are responsible. DataCite DOIs. (Agreement with DataCite) For citation, but not for management.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, all datasets have PID. Data center AERIS provides them. Implicit in the AERIS contract that they are responsible. DataCite DOIs. (Agreement with DataCite) For citation, but not for management.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	This is a strategy and being implementation. It is a policy, described in DMP on PID section.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	under implementation
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes, official policy. Carbon Portal assigns. no exceptions
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	Yes, official policy. Carbon Portal assigns. no exceptions
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	No PID system is used, but there are internal identifiers.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, EISCAT is using the Handle system
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Depends, every should have a Unique Identifiers, UUIDs (sometimes internal), some are using DOIs. There are many identifiers as well. Increasing awareness for DOIs. SIOS is recommending DOIs, but the documentation is being developed at the moment. Not likely to end up with a single PID system
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Every record should have a Unique Identifiers, UUIDs (sometimes internal), some data providers are using DOIs, which are recommended by SIOS. Responsibility for providing identifiers relies on partners data centers.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Not a policy. Preference to have a DOI (Eudat), unless there are local solutions. Not a centralised system (yet). Discussion on having data cite DOIs for at least eLTER level products. PIDs are being developed for the individual site definitions.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	No centralised system now, as the eLTER CDN is still in development. This will include DataCite DOI for SO datasets and data products. For the site documentation a PID (deims.id) is implemented to allow unambiguous identification. For historic/legacy data DataCite DOIs by B2SHARE are used. In addition, local PID systems implemented at the eLTER facilities are existing.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Will be implemented by following GEDE-RDA biodiversity WG recommendations (together with DiSSCo, etc.). Not agreed policy on the PIDs yet. Not a policy, but a practice and a principle
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	Following 2020 comment we are now in W.I.P. and initial deployment
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Well understood in the community - actively discussed for a long time. Intent in DiSSCo is to unify the current practices. Specimen level PID vs. data set PIDs. Internal PIDs might not all be globally resolvable. Some secondary data/metadata might need more work on PIDs. DiSSCo works in the global level, which requires discussion outside of Europe.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Yes. Each Digital Specimen has a PID. We are also promoting use of ORCID, RoR, Wikidata identifiers.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	DMP mentions each dataset must have a DOI. AnaEE data centre will assign on in the dataset revision system.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes, but various PID schemes used

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	3. Persistent identifiers: Do your datasets have PIDs? Are there exceptions?
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Data policy (officially approved) requires use of DOI for the datasets. This reflects to future (DANUBIUS) data, not historical data. DMP will have more on the PIDs for traceability & security perspective. The organisation assigning the DOI/PIDs is not decided, but most likely will be the DANUBIUS data portal (but a challenge). Data centre should be in control of the data ingest and publication in the approved workflow principles.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	DOI approved by DANUBIUS BGR in DMP. Persistent handler considered for historical data
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Yes, at least at the level of a float with the WMO number that is unique For the whole dataset the PID is: http://doi.org/10.17882/42182
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	The whole Argo dataset have a DataCite PID is: http://doi.org/10.17882/42182 Each individual Argo float has a unique WMO number PID.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Yes

Table 21. Category Provenance/Citation/Acknowledgement. Raw answers to the question Which PID(s) do you use? Are they internal or external?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	3.1 Which PID(s) do you use? Are they internal or external?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Usually DOIs (DataCite)- soon EPIC (for internal PIDs, still planned but very likely)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	DOI for citable datasets (data products) ePIC PID (internal) for low level datasets (files part of data products)
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	DOIs, policy agreed across the data centres.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	ePIC, DOIs, policy agreed across the data centres.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	External (DataCite), DOIs. (mainly collections) PIDs (handle) for all (including raw) data Carbon portal concept paper defines.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	The DOIs are issued via DataCite but using an ICOS-specific prefix. The basic Handles are issued via ePIC, again with an ICOS-specific prefix. Read more in chapter 5 of the ENVRplus deliverable D6.3 – Report on identification and citation service case studies (https://www.envriplus.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/D6.3.pdf)
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	internal
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, EISCAT is using the Handle System for persistent identification of all datasets.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	See above
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	See above. SIOS is harvesting metadata records, some have internal identifiers, some external.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Heterogenous (depends on centre). Typically internal for the catalogue. External DOIs for the data. Ambition to PIDs to semantics for linking parts of the RI together (people, models, etc.)
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Heterogenous (depends on centre). Typically internal for the catalogue. External DOIs for the data. Ambition to PIDs to semantics for linking parts of the RI together (people, models, etc.)
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Now use PIDs which are compliant with communities (different ones in marine (GBIF/OBIS) vs. molecular data). We are implementing test cases in invasive marine species. Internal references to LifeBlock to follow the data (see q.2.1). External PIDs you are capability for DataCite DOIs.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	We have WIP about requesting common PIDs (DOI) but also providing PIDs through LifeBlock
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	DataCite for datasets used in the community Specimen & collection level still requires harmonisation. FAIR digital object architecture & EOSC are the background policies.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Our current implementation is Handle PID systems. In the near future this will be part of DOI landscape. We are also promoting use of ORCID, RoR, Wikidata identifiers.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	DOIs (provider being negotiated) Internal pointers, URLs, which try to be as persistent as possible.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	various: UUID, DataCite, arbitrary; may be internal or external (e.g., DataCite)
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	DOI (externally)
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	DOI (externally), also handler (internal) for historical data
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	DOI (DataCite), WMO number (World Meteorological Organisation) - both external Decided at international level. Locally controlled at European level.
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	We use DataCite DOI and WMO platform code number (World Meteorological Organisation). Both are external, managed at international level.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	Both external PIDs and DOIs depending on facility

Table 22. Category Curation. Raw answers to the question Does your data service have a service level agreement (or other way to define uptime goals, etc.)?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	8. Service availability: Does your data service have a service level agreement (or other way to define uptime goals, etc.)?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Right now no, but probably certification process will clarify.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	not yet, Certification still in progress
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	no, but planned.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	no
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Probably related to FAIR certification. The current situation does not have guaranteed uptimes, etc., but in practice 99,5%
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	No formal SLA exists, from the point of view of ICOS vis-a-vis our end users. (There are agreements with the external data centers where we store/will store replicates of our data.) The system availability is monitored constantly (with Grafana) and reported annually as one of the KPIs. Was 99.6% over 2020-2022.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	No
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	No
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	no formal agreement, but in reality 98.5 availability for SIOS services
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	no formal agreement, but in reality 98.5 availability for SIOS services
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	For the DEIMS best effort basis. no defined agreements at the moment.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	not at the moment
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	LW ERIC is defining those SLAs with our providers to be able to define aggregated SLAs to our (LW ERIC) final clients There will be, mainly based on computed aggregation of SLAs from our providers, as duly applied by any large-scale (distributed) RI.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Not developed but planned.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	We have outlined TRL level expectation for the next few years in the DiSSCo Prepare output
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Based on large commercial cloud provider, with related SLAs, uptimes, disaster management, security, etc.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	24/7 is intended. So, decision on the actual service KPIs etc. But there are internal KPIs for individual service use and users' satisfaction.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	two global data central synchronised data centres, at least one is guaranteed to work. Monitoring of the data centres is done, and statistics are followed annually, 99.x% availability. Independent monitoring from IOC JCOMMOPS center (http://www.jcommops.org/board?t=argo).
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	EuroARGO GDAC is operated by Ifremer who have an ISO9001 certification that includes the process "P14: develop and administer IT services" and "P8: Collect and make available data on the marine environment". Both processes have SLAs.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	High level SLA for now

Table 23. Category Curation. Raw answers to the question Is there a policy for keeping data and metadata constantly available?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	9. Is there a policy for keeping data and metadata constantly available?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Should be, but no decision yet.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	not yet, Certification still in progress
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	90% goal for data & metadata availability. Not in DMP, but in the technical definition of the data centre.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	90% goal for data & metadata availability. Not in DMP, but in the technical definition of the data centre.
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes, carbon portal, raw data straight from the field to CP, and always available from the CP. Probably related to FAIR certification
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	No
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	No explicit policy for that
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	It is a practice, but not a policy. A science system, but not operational system. But running on the same infra as in the operational system.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	It is a practice, but not a policy. A science system, but not operational system. But running on the same infra as in the operational system.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	no.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	not at the moment
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Not a policy on this yet.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Yes, at least in practice, being developed.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Yes. this is being developed.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	If a platform as a long-term storage, they can use. These can not be necessarily guaranteed by AnaEE but are guaranteed by them. Cloud data/metadata guaranteed by AnaEE.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes, replicated ICS-C portal system on sites in two different countries
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Is agreed on the overall level.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	included in DMP
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	yes
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Yes, all data and metadata are online at https://doi.org/10.17882/42182 The latest version and the successive previous monthly snapshots are online.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on a common approach

Table 24. Category Curation. Raw answers to the question 5. Retention: Do you have a policy for retention of data and metadata?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	5. Retention: Do you have a policy for retention of data and metadata?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	No. Perhaps part of the DMP
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	no
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Not a policy, but general consensus (at least 10 years, needs confirmation)
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Not a policy, but general consensus (at least 10 years, needs confirmation)
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	No sustainability is a value, projects are offered sustainable storage of the data. Data policy requires to store the data for the period of ICOS, permanent repository afterwards. B2SAFE for security reasons.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Raw data is destroyed (but store as much as resources permit). Data products are intended to be kept indefinitely. This official policy.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	yes, most of the raw data is destroyed. Some can be stored if resources permit. All data products are intended to be kept indefinitely as part of the EISCAT agreement that has been signed by the member countries.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Interoperability requires OAI-PMS. OAI-PMH has support for incremental harvest and identification of deleted datasets. For CSW we have to wipe the catalogue on a regular basis. Metadata daily harvested. Data deletion is not supported by many data centres. Full cleanup periodically. Flagging the metadata links if dead. Still learning from the harvesting process and trying to set up a policy. Most of the data are scientific, not deleted, but could be superseded. Some model output etc. is dead after while. Practice, not a policy.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Interoperability requires OAI-PMS. OAI-PMH has support for incremental harvest and identification of deleted datasets. For CSW we have to wipe the catalogue on a regular basis. Metadata daily harvested. Data deletion is not supported by many data centres. Full cleanup periodically. Flagging the metadata links if dead. Still learning from the harvesting process and trying to set up a policy. Most of the data are scientific, not deleted, but could be superseded. Some model output etc. is dead after while. Practice, not a policy.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	no policy on eLTER level products. Not a written policy, practice to keep at least the metadata (as the data storage is not always in the central repository).
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	NO policy on eLTER level products. Not a written policy, practice to keep at least the metadata (as the data storage is not always in the central repository).
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Not a policy. But nothing is ever thrown away. However, proper agreements with data provider institutions are being agreed in order to guarantee long-term data preservation (LTDP). In fact, one of our outstanding references is the e-IRG working document on LTDP. In the particular case where LW ERIC is the original data provider, proper retention policies will be applied to (meta-)data.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	not a policy, but community of practice: specimen record is retained for perpetuity. Some secondary external digital data might be problematic (e.g., size, raw data etc.), especially outside connections. DataCite also requires this.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	NO. But community of practice is there, specimen record is retained for perpetuity. DiSSCo will be in charge of creating and enforcing the retention policy for the digital specimen data. Some of these are being under development as part of the PID implementation. Work in progress
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Yes, all is kept part of the DMP (stated) Big capacity for the storage needs.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	No updates

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	5. Retention: Do you have a policy for retention of data and metadata?
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	this varies among asset suppliers; they re obliged to keep available any asset described by metadata in the portal catalog
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Discussion on this but foreseen to be a long-term (25-30yr). Should be mapped at least as long and all data/metadata should be kept. no decision made.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	yes, in principle, 25yrs data preservation time has been discussed and agreed, not formally approved. The policy will be included in the next versions of DP and DMP in progress
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	yes, everything is kept as much as possible, as much technical data is included as possible. European level all data could be re-processed. Practice, not policy. ARGO data management level includes long-term preservation in US NCEI. Long-term archives. Data distribution and preservation are separated. https://www.EuroARGO.eu/Activities/Data-Management/Argo-Data-System
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Everything is kept as much as possible, as much technical data is included as possible. At European level all original data is preserved and regularly re-processed. Argo data management policy includes long-term preservation in US NCEI. Data distribution and preservation are distinct and documented on https://www.EuroARGO.eu/Activities/Data-Management/Argo-Data-System
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on a common approach

Table 25. Curation. Raw answers to the question Do you have a described data deletion / reduction process?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	<i>5.1. Do you have a described data deletion / reduction process?</i>
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	See above.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	no
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	Not in DMP but discussed. Not all data available in the web interface, only last version data available in the interface.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	no
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	no nothing is ever thrown away. Official policy.
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	Yes, for raw data.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, raw data is destroyed.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	see above
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	see above
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	no policy on this yet
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	No process at the moment.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Not in place.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	no but it could happen and would be necessary (e.g., geoinformation for species collection). Has no been considered in the DiSSCo context but could be an important aspect.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Not yet. The use case of hiding or removing sensitive species geographic location has been considered and it is in the roadmap.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	no except if the data provider (PI) requests data removal (= GDPR compliance)
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	this varies among asset suppliers; we have tombstone metadata
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	no policy on deleting data
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	discussions are running on this matter, no decision yet
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	no, the dataset is continuously expanded
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	No, all data and metadata are preserved.
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on a common approach

Table 26. Curation. Raw answers to the question Do you have a policy/plan for data/metadata availability in the long run (e.g., closure of the RI)?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	5.2. Do you have a policy/plan for data/metadata availability in the long run (e.g., closure of the RI)?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	CoreTrustSeal certification -> this will be fixed as a policy during 2021. AERIS will be responsible of long-term storage & availability (contractual)
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes, described in the IAGOS preservation plan; https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/iagos_preservation-plan_v1 CoreTrustSeal certification still in progress
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	no.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	no
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	Yes, there is official exit plan (part of the statutes)
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	The plan is to maintain all the landing page contents; possibly in the form of static webpages (i.e., not dynamic ones as is the case now) created by "dumping" the metadata catalogue contents at the point in time when ICOS would "end".
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	There is a policy - stakeholders should take over the data handling.
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Yes, the existing policy requires that the EISCAT member countries should take over the data handling.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	Data management plan suggest that the observation data will be available at least 10 years from the SIOS access point (in the case that SIOS is closed etc.). Partner institutions have longer time sustainability and mandate.
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	Data management plan suggest that the observation data will be available at least 10 years from the SIOS access point (in the case that SIOS is closed etc.). Partner institutions have longer time sustainability and mandate.
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Data is locally held / EUDAT etc. Metadata is unknown at the moment. Partner organisations take care of the metadata at the moment.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Data held in the EUDAT B2SHARE repo, the EUDAT policies apply. For the services run in the frame of the eLTER RI development (DEIMS-SDR, DAR, CDN, EcoSense) it is managed at best practice ensuring the long-term availability. For historic/legacy dataset (level 0) provided by the eLTER facilities this is taken care on the local or national level. This will be formalised with the establishment of the ERIC in late 2025.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Handled by the statutes. All the assets (inc. data) go back to the countries responsible (for holding in perpetuity)
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Providers provide data in the national level, but central level aggregation would be lost. Some of the technical choices are chosen to avoid lock into specific implementations. Upcoming development in the future.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	DiSSCo is working on the availability policy for the digital specimen record (which comes from various data providers who will have their own policies).
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	External party making long-term storage solution. (CNRS CCIN2P3 infrastructure in Lyon, France)
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes, each asset supplier maintains sustainable assets with metadata
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	no.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	DANUBIUS Preservation Policy as specified in DP
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Mentioned above on long-term preservation
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Yes, the Argo long-term data archive is US NCEI (the data centre infrastructure of NOAA)
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on a common approach

Table 27. Raw answers to the question Generally, do you have the RI policies/practices published in a findable and accessible way? Do they have PIDs?

<i>RI</i>	<i>Survey</i>	10. Policy availability. Generally, do you have the RI policies/practices published in a findable and accessible way? Do they have PIDs?
<i>IAGOS</i>	2020	Yes, DOIs for products. The documents on the website are not such that would have PIDs. Data policy does not have a PID. Standard operating procedures are available. There is no general rule or policy to have the policies available on the website.
<i>IAGOS</i>	2023	yes DMP, data policy available on website in open access no DOI yet
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2020	(Data policies in attachment, findable), will be part of ERIC development.
<i>ACTRIS</i>	2023	Yes, as soon as ACTRIS-ERIC is operational. Will have PID later/under implementation
<i>ICOS</i>	2020	In general, this is the goal, management plan is work in progress. Most important things available from the website (some have DOIs). Own repository (openly available, findable).
<i>ICOS</i>	2023	Policies for personal data/privacy, terms-of-use, and cookies can be accessed directly from the ICOS web site. (Not always so easy to find, though.) Management plan part 1 has been published., see https://www.icos-cp.eu/event/1238 PIDs - Most of the documents in "WS3 list" are available on our website, but usually without DOI (perhaps should add a DOI column to the questionnaire?)
<i>EISCAT</i>	2020	No
<i>EISCAT</i>	2023	Not really. The policies are written in the EISCAT Blue Book, but that is not clearly stated. Practices are not published.
<i>SIOS</i>	2020	SIOS DMP and Data policy are in the website. Interoperability guidelines in GitHub. https://sios-svalbard.org/Documents
<i>SIOS</i>	2023	<u>Documents are available on the website: https://sios-svalbard.org/Documents and also on the gitHub (https://github.com/SIOS-Svalbard/)</u>
<i>eLTER</i>	2020	Deliverables are available on the website for the projects done. Governance data management deliverable are taken as a starting point for the PPP - this could come as a policy for the eLTER.
<i>eLTER</i>	2023	Deliverables are available on the website for the projects done. Governance data management deliverable are taken as a starting point for the PPP - this could come as a policy for the eLTER.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2020	Publish every decision transparently in your website. There is the internal PID. This is a requirement in the LifeWatch ERIC statutes.
<i>LifeWatch</i>	2023	- same as 2020
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2020	Working on the DiSSCo knowledge base, will come alive in few months. Will have PID.
<i>DiSSCo</i>	2023	Our knowledge base is online, and it is being populated with different policy information. A self-assessment policy tool is under construction: https://github.com/DiSSCo/policytool
<i>AnaEE</i>	2020	Yes, but not approved. SEISM application this far used internally - this is supposed to publish all these when AnaEE is approved.
<i>AnaEE</i>	2023	Still working on it. Right now, DMP and other normative documents are on public URIs, but it's rather hard to find them, however we are definitely going to fix this issue.
<i>EPOS</i>	2020	
<i>EPOS</i>	2023	yes - published on website / URLs. No PID's yet.
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2020	Should be available on the portal (when it comes).
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	2023	no updates, same status
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2020	Each significant document has a DOI, are published in Ocean Best Practices(https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/).
<i>EUROARGO</i>	2023	Each significant Argo data management document has a DOI (user, format, qc manuals, cookbooks). They are also published in Ocean Best Practices https://www.oceanbestpractices.org .
<i>EMSO</i>	2020	
<i>EMSO</i>	2023	It depends on facility, working on a common approach

Table 28. URL links to RI data policies.

RI	Data Policy
<i>IAGOS</i>	https://www.iagos.org/data-policy/
<i>ACTRIS</i>	https://intranet.actris.eu/index.php/s/NytzH7PBGgssqZG?dir=undefined&openfile=44777
<i>ICOS</i>	https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/about-data-portal/data-license
<i>EISCAT</i>	https://eiscat.se/scientist/data/https://eiscat.se/projects/eosc/
<i>SIOS</i>	https://www.sios-svalbard.org/sites/sios-svalbard.org/files/common/SIOS_Data_Policy.pdf
<i>eLTER</i>	Not yet published
<i>LifeWatch</i>	https://www.lifewatchitaly.eu/en/data-policy-eng/
<i>DiSSCo</i>	Not yet operational. https://www.dissco.eu/dissco/technical-infrastructure/
<i>AnaEE</i>	https://www.anaee.eu/sites/anaee/files/Mediatheque/Resourcess/reportsdocuments/std_-_v_7.1_-_appendix_6_-_16.10.2020.pdf
<i>EPOS</i>	https://gnss-metadata.eu/Guidelines/EPOS-Data_Policy.pdf
<i>DANUBIUS</i>	not yet implemented
<i>EUROARGO</i>	https://argo.ucsd.edu/organization/argo-data-system/ https://www.EuroARGO.eu/Activities/Data-Management/Argo-Data-System https://www.EuroARGO.eu/policies
<i>EMSO</i>	https://emso.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/EMSO-ERIC_WEBSITE_Terms-and-conditions.pdf , http://data.emso.eu ?